

MASTER'S FINAL PROJECT

**ELABORATION OF PROCEDURE FOR
ENERGETIC AUDITS OF THE
REFRIGERATION, HEATING AND HOT
SANITARY WATER FACILITIES IN THE
HOTEL SECTOR IN MOROCCO**

MASTER IN EFFICIENCY AND ENERGY USE (MYAE)

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Abstract

Morocco is one of the best tourist destinations in the world. Hence, the tourism sector is considered an important economic pillar of the country and a social and cultural development driver. However, it is not only necessary to improve the aesthetics of tourist accommodation but also to reduce the energy consumption of this sector while maintaining the same comfort for the customer and even better. As an active actor in environmental protection, Morocco aims to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (e.g., 7, 8, 9 and 12) to deal with climate change. The purpose of this TFM is to develop a procedure as well as technical data sheets for carrying out energy audits of refrigeration, heating, and domestic hot water installations in the hotel sector in Morocco.

Keywords: Domestic hot sanitary water, Energy Audit, Heating, Hotel sector, Refrigeration, Morocco.

Resumen

Marruecos es uno de los mejores destinos turísticos del mundo. Así, el sector turístico es considerado un importante pilar económico del país y un motor de desarrollo social y cultural. Sin embargo, no sólo es necesario mejorar la estética de los alojamientos turísticos sino también reducir el consumo energético de este sector manteniendo el mismo confort para el cliente o incluso mejorándolo. Además, como actor activo en la protección del medio ambiente, Marruecos aspira a alcanzar los Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible (ODS) (p. ej., 7, 8, 9 y 12) para hacer frente al cambio climático. El presente TFM tiene por objeto desarrollar un procedimiento, así como fichas técnicas para la realización de auditorías energéticas de las instalaciones de refrigeración, calefacción y agua caliente sanitaria del sector hotelero en Marruecos.

Palabras claves : Auditoría energética, Agua caliente sanitaria, Calefacción, Marruecos, Refrigeración, Sector hotelero,

Résumé

Le Maroc est l'une des meilleures destinations touristiques au monde. Ainsi, le secteur du tourisme est considéré comme un pilier économique important du pays et un moteur de développement social et culturel. Cependant, il faut non seulement améliorer l'esthétique des hébergements touristiques mais aussi réduire la consommation d'énergie de ce secteur tout en gardant le même confort pour le client voire l'améliorer. De plus, autant qu'un acteur actif dans la protection d'environnement, le Maroc vise à atteindre les objectifs de développement durable (ODD) (ex, 7, 8, 9 et 12) pour faire face au changement climatique. L'objet de ce TFM est d'élaborer une procédure ainsi que des fiches techniques pour la réalisation des audits énergétiques des installations de réfrigération, de chauffage et d'eau chaude sanitaire dans le secteur hôtelier au Maroc.

Mots clés : Audit énergétique, Chauffage, Eau chaude sanitaire, Maroc, Réfrigération, Secteur hôtelier,

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TITLE: ELABORATION OF PROCEDURE FOR ENERGETIC AUDITS OF THE REFRIGERATION, HEATING AND HOT SANITARY WATER FACILITIES IN THE HOTEL SECTOR IN MOROCCO

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To my family,

INTRODUCTION

Morocco is one of the best tourist destinations in the world thanks to its beautiful nature and heritage sites, geographical position close to Europe, culture diversity (African and European influence) and its political stability among the North African countries. Besides, out of 140 countries, Morocco was classified as the 28th safest and secure country for tourists and passed the most popular tourist countries such as Germany (41st), UK (45th) and France (51st) [1]. Consequently, since 2013 the tourism sector registered the highest number of tourists out of the African continent [2]. The tourism industry in Morocco is counted as a significant foreign exchange source after the phosphate industry. In 2018, Morocco ranked the first place at the continental level with a number of 12.3 million international tourist arrivals which represented an increase of 8.3% comparing to the previous year (2017) **Table 1** [3] and achieved 13 million tourists in 2019 where the main arrivals are from Spain, France, Italy, UK, and Netherland respectively [4]. According to the Ministry of Tourism, Handicrafts, Air Transport and Social Economy, Morocco reached the 20th place globally in 2020 and merged itself as a reference for the Mediterranean region in terms of sustainable development [5].

Rank	Destination	International tourist arrivals in 2018 (in Million)	International tourist arrivals in 2017 (in Million)
1	Morocco	12.3	11.3
2	Egypt	11.3	8.3
3	South Africa	10.5	10.3
4	Tunisia	8.3	7.1
5	Algeria	ND ¹	2.5
6	Zimbabwe	2.6	2.4
7	Ivory Coast	2.0	1.8
8	Botswana	ND	1.6
9	Namibia	ND	1.5
10	Mozambique	ND	1.4

Table 1 - Rank of African countries in term of international tourists' arrivals

Source: World Tourism Organization (UNWTO)

In 2017, the Kingdom of Morocco has participated as a partner of the International year of Sustainable Tourism for Development aiming to follow and reach the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the lens set of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Moreover, on the same occasion, Morocco has been the latest country joining the United Nation World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), and has pledged to support the promotion of the first African Charter on Sustainable and Responsible Tourism signed over the Ministerial Forum on Tourism and Climate in Africa during the COP22 in Marrakech – Morocco (2015) [6].

¹ ND: No available Data

Although the current status of the sanitary crisis (covid-19), we are facing, has created turmoil over all plans on a global scale and more specifically on the tourism sector, and in regards to Morocco, which would be difficult for it to reach its goal of receiving 20 million tourists by this year 2020 [7], yet it is still always maintaining its optimistic vision of following its strategic plan and attaining its settled goals.

Given all of the above and in order to continue to make the tourism sector one of the main supports of the Moroccan economy as well as a driver of its social and cultural development [5], it is important to enhance and to prioritize the development of tourist accommodation. Therefore, the Ministry of Tourism has already attached a particular importance to tourist accommodation because they are considered as the main links in the tourist chain and a determining factor in the choice of tourist destination, whether at national or international level, and this translated into an increase in the number of beds in tourist accommodation structures from 97,000 in 2001 to more than 251,200 at the end of 2017 and aimed at building 200,000 new additional beds in order to accommodate more visitors according to the objectives set for the 2024 plan [5].

considering all the efforts put in place, we must not only improve the aesthetics of tourist accommodation but also take an interest in the energy consumption side in order to reduce its electric bill while maintaining the same comfort for the customer and even better as well as to share in facing the climate change and achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (e.g. 7,8,9 and 12). For this, the objective of this master thesis will be to carry out a procedure for an energy audit related to the refrigeration, heating, and hot sanitary water facilities intended for the hotel sector based on the ISO 50002 standard.

This master thesis will be divided into three sections; the first section will be dedicated to introducing the different types of tourists lodging in Morocco with their characteristics and location. Then in the second section we will present the energy audit process, the required steps to conduct it as well as the different measurement tools needed to collect the necessary data. Finally, in the last section we will apply the energy audit process to a hotel located in Casablanca.

1. TYPES OF TOURIST ACCOMMODATION

1.1. Definitions

According to the ministry of tourism, there are several types of tourist accommodation in Morocco, defined by the law 61-00 on the status of tourist establishments as follow [8];

- a. **Cottage:** is an institution with reduced accommodation capacity, located in a rural area on hiking routes or near tourist sites, which can offer a catering

service. It can be fitted out inside a private home or built as an annex to it, respecting the architectural aspect of the region. The cottage has the character of a family farm. It is said to be a "refuge" when it is located in the high mountains or near ski resorts.

- b. Hotel:** is an establishment which obligatorily offers rented rooms and/or suites equipped, to passing or staying customers. It can also provide catering services for certain categories.
- c. Conference palace and center:** a designed property mainly to receive and serve congress attendees. It must include the equipment necessary to offer all the technical services required for the organization and conduct of national or international conferences and congresses. The center is called a conference centre when it offers catering services and includes accommodation, entertainment, as well as a business center, shopping center and exhibition areas.
- d. Tourist residence:** is a tourist accommodation establishment that offers furnished accommodation units with kitchens for rental. The residence can be designed in the form of individual accommodation units or grouped in complexes or buildings, each with common facilities and services for entertainment, leisure and incidentally catering. The tourist residence must have common management.
- e. Guest house:** is an institution built in the form of an old residence, a Riad, a palace, a kasbah or a villa and located either in the medina, or in tourist routes or in sites of high tourist value.
- f. Hostel:** is a small accommodation and restaurant establishment, located outside urban areas, in a natural setting. It must offer its customers a la carte and menu meals.
- g. Motel:** is located near a main road, outside or near their agglomerations, which rents isolated accommodation units in the form of pavilions, or grouped in bungalow, independent and each one with a complete sanitary installation. The main customers of this kind of accommodation are the road users. The motel is equipped also with a garage or carport which must be in the immediate vicinity of the rooms offered to customers and must afford a "snack bar" or "self-service" restaurant service.
- h. Camping-Caravanning:** is an establishment located on an equipped, fenced and guarded site, which offers rental sites capable of accommodating campers equipped with the equipment necessary for their stay. It can also offer pitches equipped with fixed or rolling accommodation equipment. The camping-caravanning facility must include sanitary services (e.g. showers, toilets, laundry ...) and collective catering.

- i. **Roadhouse:** is a medium-sized establishment located outside urban agglomerations, on a tourist itinerary, offering accommodation and catering services and a service station with incidentally a small mechanical workshop.
- j. **Holiday village:** is an accommodation and leisure establishment which offers, according to the package formula, to costumers mainly made up of tourists and vacationers, isolated accommodation units or grouped together and provides catering and entertainment services adapted to this type of accommodation and costumers.
- k. **Boarding house:** is an accommodation and incidentally catering establishment, intended for staying or passing customers. Operating a pension takes a familiar and permanent character.

Furthermore, exist other form of lodging that some tourists opt for according to their preference and tourism plan, such as; bivouac, homestay and alternative accommodations. However, in our study in this project we will focus on the energy audit in hotels because they constitute a high rate energy consumer in comparison with the other types of accommodation.

1.2. Litter capacity

The number of beds and their distribution per each tourist accommodation differ from one category to another and are as follow:

Figure 1 - Evolution of classified accommodation capacity (in bed).

Source: Ministry of Tourism

<https://mtataes.gov.ma/fr/tourisme/chiffres-cles-tourisme/indicateurs-du-secteur-touristique/#>

As we can notice from **Figure 1**, the total number of beds per tourist accommodation has increased by almost 70 000 beds from 2012 to 2019 and this is due to the strategic plan that Morocco has drawn to welcome more national and international tourists.

	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	Var 19/18	Part 2019
Marrakech	56581	59298	60517	64716	67613	69496	71304	73058	2%	27%
Agadir	34014	34762	37199	37511	37924	38200	38360	38505	0%	14%
Casablanca	14472	14885	15141	15747	18751	18883	20416	21200	4%	8%
Tanger-Assilah	8568	9448	10176	10623	11571	12080	12323	13591	10%	5%
Fès	7785	8156	9429	9693	9996	10200	10248	10248	0%	4%
Ouarzazate	6384	6630	6791	6881	6978	7254	7254	7293	1%	3%
Rabat	5601	5866	5982	5982	6080	6458	6468	6468	0%	2%
Oujda-Saidia	7006	7781	7901	7913	7913	9085	9085	9149	1%	3%
Meknès	3633	3729	4452	4592	4618	4677	4699	4734	1%	2%
Ifrane	6663	8423	8542	8574	8614	8676	8730	8730	0%	3%
Essaouira-Mogador	5223	5354	5632	5876	6090	6185	6303	6481	3%	2%
El Jadida-Mazagan	2646	2674	2672	2738	2829	2793	2869	2918	2%	1%
Tétouan	1641	1653	1842	2210	2210	2220	2232	2295	3%	1%

Table 2 - Evolution by destination of hotel capacity classified in beds.

Source: Ministry of Tourism

<https://mtataes.gov.ma/fr/tourisme/chiffres-cles-tourisme/indicateurs-du-secteur-touristique/#>

From **Table 2** above we note that the number of beds is rising each year (from 2012 to 2019) in almost all moroccan touristic cities. Moreover, between the two last years (2018/2019), generally the number of beds has increased between 1% and 2%, also, there was a significant rose in beds in Tanger-Assilah region (10% in only one year), unlike Agadir, Fès, Rabat and Ifrane where the number of beds remain the same (0%). Marrakech and Agadir are the cities with higher bed capacity (27% and 14% respectively) compared to the other cities of the Moroccan Kingdom.

	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	Var 19/18	part 2019
1* Hotel	13160	14908	15447	15637	15945	16188	16413	16502	1%	6%
2* Hotel	14382	14922	15247	15671	16025	16212	16564	16962	2%	6%
3* Hotel	28884	29312	30391	31546	32549	33197	34256	35316	3%	13%
4* Hotel	41595	43249	44311	46806	49025	50456	51242	52092	2%	19%
5* Hotel	28273	28684	28610	29466	31589	32825	33499	35527	6%	13%
Luxury	4654	4832	4832	5196	5626	6052	6052	6363	5%	2%
Hotel Residences	14216	15188	17921	19109	21242	22380	23930	24718	3%	9%
Clubs Hotels	18970	19692	19692	19692	20058	20720	20975	20975	0%	8%
Guest house	20243	22185	23625	26525	27882	29519	30611	31616	3%	12%
Others*	15371	19443	22974	23902	25030	26172	27605	28763	4%	11%

*Others: Boarding house, Motel, Cottage, Camping-Caravanning, Tourist residence

Table 3 - Evolution by category of hotel capacity classified in beds. **Source:** Ministry of Tourism

<https://mtataes.gov.ma/fr/tourisme/chiffres-cles-tourisme/indicateurs-du-secteur-touristique/#>

Table 3 shows that the number of beds per tourist accommodation increases slightly each year and from 2018 to 2019 the highest percentage was dedicated to luxury hotels and 5* hotels. Furthermore, we note that in 2019 the highest total number of beds per lodging is recorded for 4* hotels with a percentage of 19% followed by 3* and 5* hotels (13% each) while houses of 'hosts represent 12% of the total number of tourist establishments and the other types participate with a percentage of less than 10%.

2. ENERGY AUDIT

The international standard ISO 50002 (2014 edition) defined the energy audits as a systematic analysis of the quantity of the energy applied (consumed) and the way or the type of energy application (e.g. processes, lighting, production lines, transportation, ventilation, cooling, and heating) during a specified energy audit scope so as to identify, quantify and point out the bargain for mended results that are related to the energy consumption, energy use and energy efficiency [9]. In this master thesis we will only focus on the energy audit related to the refrigeration, heating and hot sanitary water for the hotel sector.

According to the Norm UNE-EN 16247-2:2014 [10], related to the energy audits, the energy consumed in buildings depends mainly to the following:

- The characteristics of the building envelope;
- The behaviour of the occupant and the operational regime;
- Local weather conditions;
- The designed indoor environment conditions;
- The activities and processes in/of the building;
- The characteristics and configuration of the building's technical systems.

2.1. Energy audit process

In order to proceed the energy audit, it is required to collect the necessary information to monitor and analyse the status of the facilities and detect anomalies, hence, the resulting actions will help to accelerate and increase awareness of the need to manage energy consumption and expenditure on a sustainable basis. **Figure 2** shows the different steps of the energy audit according to the ISO 50002.

Figure 2 - Stages of the energy audit
Source: ISO 50002

The Norm UNE-EN 16247-2:2014, related to the energy audits in buildings, defines the different steps of the energy audit process as shown in **Figure 3** below:

Figure 3 - The main steps of the energy audit process.
Source: AENOR UNE-EN 16247-2:2014

2.1.1. Preliminary contact

During the preliminary contact of the energy audit we must identify all parties/organizations and their roles in the property, management, use, operation and maintenance of the building as well as their respective impacts and interests on energy use and consumption. Moreover, the scope of the audit should be agreed to cover the technical interaction of the systems within the building, and the interaction of the systems with the building. Optimizing some specific sector for the exclusion of others can give misleading results [10]

From one hand, we have to specify what we will included in the energy audit and their limits, that is to say, the type of the building and on which parts of it we will apply the energy audit, define the type of energy services of the building as well as its technical systems, the areas and systems outside of the building, and the energy performance indicators that could be used as appropriate for the energy audit [10]. From the other hand, we should take into consideration that all details in all

levels of the energy audit will impact on the level of modelling, the selection of samples, the level of measurement including subcontracting, the site spent at the site, the level of opportunities' definition for improving energy efficiency, the measurements' requirements, as well as the required auditor skills [10].

Among the principal objectives of the energy audits are the reduction of the energy consumption hence the costs as well as reducing the environmental impact and in other cases in order to comply with legislation or voluntary obligations [10].

2.1.2. Initial meeting

The initial meeting is dedicated to point out the obligatory tasks of the auditor in the field work such as the restricted access areas and the restricted access areas, the fixed time of site visits (outside/within working normal hours) and determining the level of participation of the occupant. Further, we should obtain, when available, some kind of information from the property like for example if any awareness-raising or motivation program for the building's occupants has been implemented, the occupancy patterns for the range of different activities within the building, energy certificates prepared for the building, the set points and operational limits of indoor environmental conditions (such as temperatures, air flows, illuminance, noise) and any seasonal variations, and any comments of the occupants or other part of the operational performance of the building and the level of service of the building [10].

2.1.3. Data collection

The data collection should be adequate to the energy audit scope, and follow the steps below [10]:

2.1.3.1. Information request

The organization should provide to the auditor the following data [10]:

- The current and available energy carriers;
- The energy related data:
 - Distributed, produced and exported energy, for each energy carrier;
 - Energy consumption data (or related time and date readings) from any available meter (e.g. heat meter, domestic hot water meter, fuel meter, burner hour meter);
 - Individual measurement data, if available;
 - Energy/load demand curve at short intervals (e.g. per hour), if available;
 - Any relevant related measurements.

The frequency of the up-mentioned data taken should be appropriate to the scope and level of detail of the energy audit and, when available, recorded by the construction and control system. Building energy audits typically deal with monthly consumption data.

- The adjustment factors that affect energy consumption such as:
 - Climate data (e.g. temperature, degree days, humidity, lighting) from the local building automation and control system, if available;
 - Occupation patterns;

Information needed to quantify the adjustment factors that affect energy consumption should be recorded by the building control system if available (for example, occupancy times, degree-hours, etc.).

- Information on significant changes in the last 3 years or in the period covered by the available operational data, relating to:
 - The physical form of the building;
 - Spaces - in size and/or in use;
 - The building envelope (window renovation, added insulation, etc.);
 - The technical systems of the building and the areas they serve;
 - Tenant plans;
 - Occupation of the spaces (different times of occupation, behaviour in extended hours and internal loads);
 - Setpoints and occupant behaviour;
- Values to use, adapted to local / national performance indicators (if applicable):
 - Surface, building volume...
- Existing documents and information on design, operation and maintenance, such as:
 - Plans of the building as it is built;
 - Any external factors that may influence the energy performance of the building (for example, shading by trees or adjacent buildings);
 - Indications of supplied building services (e.g. which rooms or areas are heated, cooled, ventilated) on the floor plan of the building;
 - Diagrams of the technical system of the building, indicating the zones of the system, if any;
 - Diagrams and control configuration;
 - Data and ratings of devices and components;
- The building information model (BIM) and/or building design models, if available;
- Equipment that uses energy in occupied spaces and other internal loads.

2.1.3.2. *Review of available data*

The available data collected during the energy audit must be reviewed following the instructions below [10]:

- Review the information collected and provided by the organization;
- Review the scope and limits of the energy audit if deemed appropriate once initial information has been received;
- Judge whether the information provided by the organization allows the energy audit process to continue and achieve the agreed objectives;

- When data is missing the client will be given the option to present the missing data or accept that the auditor will make assumptions (which will be clearly detailed);
- Based on experience and competence, choose the systems that use energy and the elements to be verified on-site, depending on the objective, scope and level of detail of the energy audit.

2.1.3.3. Preliminary data analysis

After collecting the necessary data and review it, we should undertake a preliminary analysis of the energy balance of the audited object on the basis of energy data and establish the relevant adjustment factors as well as the pertinent energy performance indicators then, if possible, evaluate the distribution of energy consumption (breakdown of consumption) depending on the measured data, and if there is sufficient information, we should establish an initial energy reference to use in order to quantify the impacts of energy saving interventions. Further, we must plan the subsequent data collection and measurement to be carried out during the field work. Finally, during the energy audit we must develop a preliminary list of opportunities for improving energy efficiency [10].

Note: In the case of our study which is related only to the refrigeration, heating and hot sanitary water facilities, and according to norm EN 16247-3, related to energy audits of processes, we would follow the list example of data needed presented below [11]:

- a. General information on company performance:
 - i. Processed / manufactured products;
 - ii. Daily / annual production;
 - iii. Name of the energy officer;
 - iv. Name of the transportation officer;
 - v. Operating times;
 - vi. Starting and stopping points;
 - vii. Shift patterns.

- b. Cooling towers:
 - i. Description of the system, installed capacity and details of its adjustment to operational needs;
 - ii. Types and number of machines (air-cooled, water-cooled, evaporation);
 - iii. Thermal capacity;
 - iv. Temperatures;
 - v. Control;
 - vi. Measurement;
 - vii. General condition of the material and the distribution network (system, pump);
 - viii. Number of hours of operation;
 - ix. Annual energy and water consumption.

- c. Heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC);
 - i. Description of the system, installed capacity and details of its adjustment to operational needs;
 - ii. Analysis of HVAC systems;
 - iii. Nature of the heat source (distribution of fluids, fuel, electricity);
 - iv. Types of devices and power carrier distribution;
 - v. Installed capacity (global and by system);
 - vi. Heat recovery;
 - vii. Control and configuration method (zone, separation, modulation), controlled variables and adjustment variables;
 - viii. Monitoring equipment (thermometers, hygrometers, etc.);
 - ix. Utilization rate;
 - x. General condition of the devices and the distribution duct systems;
 - xi. Annual consumption levels by system.

- d. Sanitary hot water (DHW);
 - i. Description of the system, installed capacity and details of its adjustment to operational needs;
 - ii. Principle of production (centralized, independent, mixed, etc.);
 - iii. Material characteristics (power, temperature, fluid pressure, etc.);
 - iv. Storage (temperature, insulating material, etc.);
 - v. Distribution description and characteristics: storage tanks (capacity, coupling), circulation pumps (flow, pressure), regulation, network (diameter, number of outgoing lines), insulating material;
 - vi. Domestic hot water needs, number of points served;
 - vii. Condition of the equipment and the distribution network;
 - viii. Measurement;
 - ix. Annual consumption.

2.1.4. Field work

2.1.4.1. *Field work objective*

Throughout the field work, as energy auditors, we must inspect the site with respect to the data already received, assess for each significant building service the actual and future service level (viz. temperature, humidity, illuminance level, etc.), verify that the technical systems are adequate for the intended purpose, that is, that they can provide the required level of service, understand the drivers of changes in technical systems, such as seasonal demands, also we should evaluate the performance of technical systems, taking into consideration the system and the control of generation, storage, distribution and emission, finally we should not forget to look for opportunities to improve energy efficiency and related limitations and restrictions [10].

2.1.4.2. *Conduct*

During the field work, we should [12]:

- Ensure that measurements and observations are made reliably and in situations representative of normal operation and, where appropriate, under

appropriate climatic conditions; It is accepted that it may be advantageous to make observations and measurements outside normal working hours, during rest periods or when a special climatic load is not expected;

- Promptly inform the organization of any unforeseen difficulties that arise during the performance of its work.

2.1.4.3. *Site visits*

During the site visits,

From one part, the property should [12]:

- Designate at least one person (if necessary), with the essential powers and authority to carry out direct operations on the processes and equipment if needed, to guide and accompany the audit personnel;
- Provide access to documentation such as; plans, manuals and other technical documents relevant to the installations along with the results of any tests that have been carried out.

From another part, the auditor should ask the property to provide with the following information [10]:

- Authorized assistance for any tests/trials and any operations required in the energy audit, (for example, turning systems and equipment on or off);
- Access (read-only) to the building automation and control system, and electronic data sources;
- Access to the parts of the building that are defined as relevant to perform the energy audit.

2.1.5. Analysis

2.1.5.1. *Breakdown of energy*

During the energy audit the energy breakdown should be representative of energy input and energy use, also, we should clarify which energy flows are based on measurements and which on estimates/calculations. the following breakdown should be detailed:

- The breakdown of the final use of energy by the service and other use in absolute or specific figures and in coherent energy units (for example, pie charts);
- The breakdown of energy distributed by energy carrier in terms of consumption, cost and emissions in coherent units (e.g. pie charts);
- The inventory of energy production installed on site and its export to third parties, in absolute figures, if applicable.

2.1.5.2. *Energy performance indicators*

The analysis should include some indicators such as the calculation of energy performance indicators (specific energy use) or specific building baselines, and the metrics used must be agreed between the auditor and the property [10].

2.1.5.3. *Opportunities to improve energy efficiency*

In order to improve the energy efficiency we should identify opportunities based on the comparison with benchmarks (when applicable), the age and condition of the buildings and technical systems, how they are operated and maintained, technology systems and existing equipment compared to the best available technology, the best practices without ignoring the auditor's experience .

2.1.6. Report

2.1.6.1. *Report content*

The report contains all the recommendations related to future measurement as well as verification methods for the proposed energy saving interventions mentioned in the following categories [10]:

- Low cost measures (for example, adaptation of the operating mode, reduction of supply losses, etc.);
- High cost measures (for example, building exterior, technical construction equipment, etc.);
- Review of the comfort, health and wellness requirements (e.g. temperature and humidity level, room size, etc.);
- Training and awareness of end users (training and motivation, and behaviour change).

2.1.7. Final meeting

The energy audit is presented and delivered during the final meeting, and the auditor must present and explain the results of the energy audit in a simple and easy way that make it understandable by the organization so that it can facilitate their decision-making regarding the energy measures to be taken [12].

2.2. Measurement tools

In this section we will present some of the different possible measurement tools used during an energy audit process.

2.2.1. Luxmeter

A lux corresponds to the illumination of a surface which receives a luminous flux of one lumen per square meter. A luxmeter is the device that measures the light illuminance received per unit area and given in lux (lx) [13].

The operation of a luxmeter is based on a photovoltaic sensor or a CCD sensor. The latter receives a photon flux that converts into an electrical signal more or less strong depending of the intensity of the received light flux. Some colours of light are more efficient at producing electrons from the energy received by photons. Luxmeters are therefore usually equipped with spectrum correction filters. They also fit through separate measurement scales, to low and high intensities [13].

Figure 4 - Digital Luxmeter with data storage.

Source: <https://es.rs-online.com>

2.2.2. Voltmeter

The voltmeter is a device that measures the difference in electrical potential (or the DC and AC voltages) between two different points. The unit of measurement called Volt (V).

Figure 5 - Voltmeter.

Source: <https://peaktech-rce.com/>

2.2.3. Ammeter

The ammeter is a device that measures the intensity of an electric current passing through a circuit. The unit of measurement is the Ampere (A).

Figure 6 - Ammeter.

Source : <https://www.reichelt.com/de/en/analoges-ampere-meter-10-a-ac-dc-peaktech-3203-p163761.html>

Note: the voltmeter, ammeter, ohmmeter as well as the thermometer could be all grouped in a single device called multi-meter as shown in **Figure 7**, some multi-meters include also a thermometer.

Figure 7 - Digital display multi-meter.

Source: <https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Multim%C3%A8tre>

2.2.4. Wattmeter

The wattmeter is a device that measures the electric power (expressed in Watts (W)) consumed by a receiver or supplied by an electric generator.

Figure 8 - Wattmeter.

Source: <https://www.telewave.com/product/rf-digital-wattmeter-model-44d/>

2.2.5. Infrared Thermometer

Infrared thermometer (also called spot radiometer) is a device that allows to measure the actual temperature at a single point (relatively small) of a machine/surface [14].

Figure 9 - Infrared thermometer.

Source: <https://www.omega.co.uk/pptst/OS758-LS.html>

2.2.6. Thermal camera

A thermal camera is a heat sensor that records the different infrared radiation (heat waves) emitted by the bodies/objects and which vary according to their temperature, then created an electronic image that can clearly show the differences of temperature based on the information collected. However, it does not allow to see behind a wall or an obstacle, it only reproduces the heat stored by a body, or shows the thermal flow of a wall due to a hearth at the back [15].

Figure 10 - Thermal camera.

Source: <https://www.flir.es/products/e75/>

2.2.7. Current clamp

A current clamp is an electrical test tool that allows, without a physical contact, the measurement of the properties of the electric current in a conductor. It has two different jaws that opened in order to allow the clamping around the electrical conductor [16].

Figure 11 - Current clamp.

Source: <https://www.welectron.com/Brymen-BM089-Current-Clamp-Multimeter>

2.2.8. Combustion analyser

A combustion analyser is a tool that measures a range of parameters (e.g. level of gases, chimney temperature and pressure, excess air, inlet temperature, combustion efficiency, monoxide CO and oxygen O₂). It is specially designed to calculate and analyse the efficiency of heaters, furnaces, and boilers [17].

Figure 12 - Combustion analyser.

Source: <https://www.creativesafety.com/industrial-combustion-analyzer/>

2.2.9. Air Velocity Meter

The air velocity meters are mainly used to detect the leakages in pipes as well as the density of air flow from an air handler. When the latter is reaching a high airflow, the fan motor can be slow down so that to save energy. There are several types of air velocity meters, namely; Anemometer, Hot Wire Anemometer, Pitot Tube, Rotating Vane Anemometer, and the Heated Thermocouple [18].

Figure 13 - Air velocity meter.

Source: https://www.pce-instruments.com/english/measuring-instruments/test-meters/air-velocity-meter-pce-instruments-multifunction-air-velocity-meter-pce-va-20-det_2776268.htm

3. CASE STUDY – HOTEL CASABLANCA

3.1. Instructions for filling the technical sheets

The following equations are used in order to fill the technical sheets [19]:

3.1.1. Boiler performance

While executing the energy audit we need to determine the performance of the thermal machine under study which is, in the case of building, the boiler:

$$\eta = 100 - q_{sh} - q_u - q_{re} - q_s(\%) \quad (1)$$

With:

q_{sh} : Losses due to sensible heat in the fumes (%)

q_u : Unburned gas losses (%)

q_{re} : Radiation, convection and conduction losses from the boiler (%)

q_s : Losses due to unburned solids (%)

Note: The boiler performance is different from the combustion performance.

$$\eta_{Boiler} = \eta_{Combustion} - q_{re} \quad (2)$$

3.1.2. Economic savings

The following formula is used to calculate the annual economic savings:

$$A = \sum_{i=1}^{NA} T_{Ai}(Q_{Ai}PQ_A + E_{Ai}PE_A) + M_A - \sum_{j=1}^{NR} T_{Rj}(Q_{Rj}PQ_R + E_{Rj}PE_R) - M_R \quad (3)$$

Where:

A: Net annual savings. Refers to the difference between the savings due to the reduction of energy consumption and the annual cost of maintenance and operation (€/ year)

T_{Ai} : Annual operating time in mode "i" at present (h / year)

T_{Rj} : Annual operating time in "j" mode after reform (h / year)

Q_{Ai} : Hourly fuel consumption in mode "i" at present (kg or l or th / h)

Q_{Rj} : Hourly fuel consumption in mode "j" after reform (kg or l or th / h)

PQ_A : Current fuel price (€/ kg or l or th / h)

PQ_R : Fuel price after reform (€/ kg or l or th / h)

E_{Ai} : Hourly electricity consumption in mode "i" at present (kWh / h)

E_{Rj} : Hourly electricity consumption in mode "j" after the reform (kWh / h)

PE_A : Current Electricity Price (€/ kWh)

PE_R : Electricity price after the reform (€ / kWh)

M_A : Current maintenance and operating costs (€ / year)

M_R : Maintenance and operation costs after the reform (€ / year)

Note: In case of that the installation only works and / or is going to work at a single operating regime (for example: flow of a pump), it will not be necessary to do any summation, if not, NA and / or NR will be equal to 1.

3.1.3. Gross amortization period

It is also known as simple pay-back or return on investment time, and calculated by the formula below:

$$PB = \frac{I}{A} \text{ (years)} \quad (4)$$

PB: Payback period (years)

I: Investment cost, includes labour and installation materials (€)

A: Net annual savings. It is the difference between the savings due to the reduction of energy consumption and the annual cost of maintenance and operation (€/ year)

3.1.4. Gross Return on Investment (G-ROI)

It is defined as the percentage ratio of the profit obtained throughout the life of the equipment with respect to the initial investment:

$$RBG = \frac{I - A_n}{I} (\%) \quad (5)$$

A_n : Total net savings. It is the sum of all the savings throughout the life of the equipment (€)

$$A_n = A \times U_L \quad (6)$$

U_L : Equipment useful life (year)

I : Investment cost, includes labour and installation materials (€)

3.1.5. Gross Annual Yield

A possible criterion for deciding on the investment may be, for example, that the Gross Annual Yield is greater than 20%:

$$RBA = \frac{RBG}{U_L} \quad (7)$$

3.1.6. Rate of Return on Investment (RRI)

The Rate of Return on Investment considers the estimated life of the equipment in terms of its depreciation. To justify the investment, it is necessary that the RRI corresponding to the analysed installation is greater than that corresponding to other investment alternatives.

$$RRI = \frac{A_n - D}{I} \quad (8)$$

D : Annual depreciation of the equipment throughout the estimated life. If we assume a linear depreciation, it would be equal to the cost of the investment divided by the number of years of estimated life of the equipment (€/year)

$$D = \frac{I}{U_L} \quad (9)$$

3.1.7. Benefit / Cost Ratio

The relationship between cost and benefit is given by the following equation:

$$B/C = \frac{VA}{I} = \frac{f \times A}{I} \quad (10)$$

B : Benefit (€)

C : Cost (€)

VA : Actual value of savings (€)

f : Factor value update. It is the coefficient by which the annual saving must be multiplied (A) to obtain the present value of the saving that will be obtained throughout the estimated years of the equipment's life (see **Table 4** below).

Interest (%)	Years								
	2	3	4	5	6	7	10	12	15
5,0	1,859	2,723	3,546	4,329	5,076	5,786	7,722	8,863	10,380
5,5	1,846	2,698	3,505	4,270	4,996	5,068	7,538	8,619	10,038
6,0	1,833	2,613	3,465	4,212	4,917	5,582	7,360	8,384	9,712
6,5	1,821	2,648	3,426	4,156	4,841	5,485	7,189	8,159	9,403
7,0	1,808	2,624	3,387	4,100	4,751	5,389	7,024	7,943	9,108
7,5	1,796	2,601	3,349	4,046	4,694	5,291	6,864	7,735	8,827
8,0	1,783	2,577	3,312	3,993	4,623	5,206	6,710	7,536	8,559
8,5	1,771	2,554	3,276	3,941	4,554	5,119	6,561	7,345	8,304
9,0	1,759	2,531	3,240	3,890	4,486	5,033	6,418	7,161	8,061
9,5	1,747	2,509	3,204	3,840	4,420	4,950	6,279	6,984	7,828
10,0	1,736	2,487	3,170	3,791	4,355	4,868	6,145	6,814	7,600
10,5	1,724	2,465	3,136	3,743	4,293	4,790	6,015	6,650	7,394
11,0	1,712	2,444	3,102	3,696	4,230	4,712	5,800	6,492	7,190
11,5	1,700	2,422	3,070	3,650	4,170	4,638	5,768	6,340	6,997
12,0	1,690	2,401	3,037	3,604	4,111	4,563	5,064	6,194	6,811
12,5	1,680	2,381	3,005	3,560	4,053	4,492	5,536	6,053	6,633
13,0	1,668	2,361	2,975	3,517	3,998	4,422	5,420	5,918	6,462
13,5	1,657	2,341	2,944	3,475	3,942	4,355	5,320	5,787	6,299
14,0	1,640	2,321	2,914	3,433	3,889	4,288	5,216	5,660	6,142
14,5	1,613	2,302	2,884	3,392	3,836	4,224	5,116	5,539	5,991
15,0	1,626	2,283	2,855	3,352	3,784	4,160	5,019	5,421	5,847
15,5	1,605	2,246	2,792	3,274	3,685	4,030	4,833	5,197	5,575
16,0	1,585	2,210	2,743	3,199	3,589	3,112	4,659	4,988	5,324
16,5	1,566	2,174	2,690	3,127	3,498	3,811	4,494	4,793	5,091
17,0	1,547	2,140	2,639	3,058	3,410	3,706	4,339	4,612	4,876
17,5	1,528	2,106	2,589	2,991	3,326	3,605	4,192	4,439	4,675

Table 4 - Coefficient (f) by which the annual saving (A) must be multiplied.

Source: [19]

3.2. Technical sheets

The technical sheets below are used to collect data related to the energy audit of the refrigeration, heating and hot sanitary water facilities [20]:

0. GENERAL DATA OF THE ENERGY AUDIT

Technical Sheet 1

0. General data of the energy audit

Date:

1. **Audit number:**
2. **Total number of buildings that is independently studied in any of the sections:**
3. **Number and name of each of the buildings that is independently studied:**

N°	Designation/Name	N°	Designation/Name
00		05	
01		06	
02		07	
03		08	
04		09	

4. **Number of times each section and buildings considered are completed:**

Section					N°
0. General data of the energy audit	00 (All)				01
1. General Building data					
2. Construction Features					
3. Energy Supplies					
4. Lighting					
5. Heating System					
6. Refrigeration System					
7. Ventilation System					
8. DHW ² system					
9. Solar Thermal Energy Installation					
10. Engines					
11. Cogeneration Facility					
12. Other Energy Equipment					
13. Solar PV ³ Energy Installation					
14. Signalling and Control Integration					
15. Concluding Remarks	00 (All)				01

5. **Author:**
6. **Company:**
7. **Signature and stamp:**

² DHW: Domestic Hot Water

³ PV: Photovoltaic

1. GENERAL BUILDING DATA

Technical Sheet 2

1. General Building data

1. Identification and location

8. Building name:

9. Company:

10. Tax Identification Code (IF):

Website:

11. Purpose:

12. Street or square:

No.:

13. Zip Code:

Location:

14. District:

2. Contact person

15. Name:

16. Position:

17. Mobile phone:

Fax:

18. E-mail:

Technical Sheet 3

1. General Building data

3. Operating system

19. Maximum building capacity: persons.

20. Description of the most common tasks in the building:

Task	Description

21. Hours, days of the week and occupation for the most common tasks:

Season of the year		From: To:			From: To:		
Rates							
Hours/Month							
Hours/Season							
Hours/Year							

22. Months in which the building is almost empty (unoccupied) for 15 or more days:

January February March April May June
 July August September October November December

2. CONSTRUCTION FEATURES

Technical Sheet 4

2. Construction Features

1. Nature, location and age of the building

23. Building type:

Conventional

Monumental

Listed

24. Location:

Exempt between buildings

Between party walls

Totally isolated

25. Environment:

Urban

Rural

Isolated

26. Approximate year of construction:

27. Years of permanence in the building manager:

28. Years since the last major construction reform:

29. Nature of the former:

30. Are you planning to carry out any modification, reform or rehabilitation of the building?

Yes

No

31. Are you planning to carry out any modification, reform or rehabilitation of the building enclosures?

Yes

No

32. If so, what percentage of the total would the reform cover?

Technical Sheet 5

2. Construction Features

33. Energy rating obtained by the building:

Energy rating	In project	Final construction
Dwelling 1		
Dwelling 2		
Dwelling 3		
Dwelling 4		
Dwelling 5		
Dwelling 6		
Dwelling 7		
Dwelling 8		
Dwelling 9		
Dwelling 10		
Building		

Technical Sheet 6

2. Construction Features

2. Surfaces and heights

34. Number of floors:

Above ground:

Below ground:

35. Useful and/or built areas and free height by floors:

Floor	Area (m ²)		Height (m)	Volume (m ³)		Floor	Area (m ²)		Height (m)	Volume (m ³)	
	Built	Used		Built	Used		Built	Used		Built	Used

36. Total areas: m² built/useful:

37. Total volumes: m³ built/useful:

3. Basic scheme(s) of the building

38. Sketch(s) of floor(s) and/or elevation(s):

Technical Sheet 7

2. Construction Features

4. Data collection of walls, floors, roofs and skylights

39. Characteristics of walls in contact with the ground, the exterior or with non-habitable spaces

Type	Insulating layer	Description

40. Sketches of type walls:

Technical Sheet 8

2. Construction Features

41. Characteristics of soils in contact with the ground or with non-habitable spaces:

Type	Insulating layer	Description

42. Sketch of type soils:

Technical Sheet 9

2. Construction Features

43. Characteristics of roofs in contact with the ground or with non-habitable spaces:

Type	Insulating layer	Description

44. Sketch of type covers:

Technical Sheet 10

2. Construction Features

45. Characteristics of openings and skylights in contact with the ground or with non-habitable spaces:

Type	Insulating layer	Description

46. Sketch of holes and type skylights:

Technical Sheet 11

2. Construction Features

1. Measurements to be taken: thermography of walls, floors, roofs and skylights

47. Thermography carried out to walls:

Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification
Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification

48. Comments:

49. Observations:

Technical Sheet 12

2. Construction Features

50. Thermography carried out on soils:

Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification
Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification

51. Comments:

52. Observations:

Technical Sheet 13

2. Construction Features

53. Thermography carried out on roofs:

Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification
Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification

54. Comments:

55. Observations:

Technical Sheet 14

2. Construction Features

56. Thermography carried out on holes and skylights:

Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification
Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification

57. Comments:

58. Observations:

Technical Sheet 15

2. Construction Features

5. Audit on constructive aspects

59. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in construction:

1. Have you observed the appearance of damp on walls or ceilings?

Yes

No

2. Do doors and windows close when the heating or air conditioning system is on?

Yes

No

3. In summer, are the awnings lowered or are the curtains drawn of the windows located on the facades facing south or west?

Yes

No

4. Is it scheduled a periodic review of doors and windows?

Yes

No

5. Are there drafts from chimneys, air ducts or ventilation holes?

Yes

No

6. Are all unheated lofts and spaces under roofs insulated?

Yes

No

7. Are doors and windows sealed?

Yes

No

8. Do the door locks work correctly?

Yes

No

9. Are heated and unheated spaces properly separated?

Yes

No

10. Are all the air chambers insulated from the facade walls?

Yes

No

Technical Sheet 16

2. Construction Features

59. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in construction:

11. Have the thermal bridges on the facade been broken?

Yes

No

12. Are roofs and roofs insulated?

Yes

No

13. Has the possibility of placing Trombe walls in single-family homes been studied?

Yes

No

14. Is there the possibility of mounting suspended ceilings?

Yes

No

15. Do you have double glazed windows or an exterior window (double window)?

Yes

No

16. In premises that are air-conditioned, do the windows located on sunny facades have reflective glass with solar laminates?

Yes

No

Technical Sheet 17

2. Construction Features

6. Constructive improvements

60. Constructive improvements justified by energy efficiency, identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion		€	
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

Higher salubrity (health)

Streams are removed

Radiation is reduced

Higher comfort

“Cold wall” is eliminated

Noises are reduced

Elimination of humidity

Others:

3. ENERGY SUPPLIES

Technical Sheet 18

3. Energy supplies

1. Types of energy

61. Energy supplies available to the building

Electricity	diesel C	Piped natural gas
Coal	LPG ⁴	Other

2. Electrical installations

62. Single-line electrical scheme(s) of the main supply and distribution circuits:

63. Details of the main supply and distribution circuits:

Circuit						
Counter						
Switch (A)						
No. cables x section (mm ²)						
Material: conduct. / isolate						
Installation form						
Length (m)						
Voltage (V): input / output						
Voltage drop (V /%)						
Measurement (Y/N, see section 4 below)						
Observations						

⁴ LPG: Liquefied Petroleum Gas

Technical Sheet 20

3. Energy supplies

4. Distribution and measurements of energy consumption

66. Distribution of average annual electricity consumption by use:

Use										
Power (kW or %)										
Energy (kWh or %)										

67. Most important parameters and results of electrical measurements:

Installation	
Computer file	
Start date/time	
End date/time	
Record intervals (s)	
Total active consumption (kWh)	
Reactive consumption (kVARh)	
cos φ medium	
Consumption RH active (%)	
Consumption FH active (%)	
Consumption OPH active (%)	
Max active power (kW)	
Average use factor (%)	
Voltage (V)	
Phase balancing	

Technical Sheet 21

3. Energy supplies

5. Fuel storage and distribution facilities

68. Principle scheme of the main fuel storage and distribution circuits:

69. Fuel tank data:

Tank					
Fuel					
Capacity (m ³)					
materials					
Age (years)					
Counters or levels					
Surface state					
Leak identification					
Purge form					

Technical Sheet 22

3. Energy supplies

6. Conditions of supply and energy consumption: fuels

70. Fuel supply contracting conditions:

Combustible: Delivery form:
 Contract number: Rate:
 Contracted power/flow: (Liter or kg. Or Nm³/day/ Te/day

71. Fuel consumption in the last days:

Billing period	Combustible consumption	
	L or kg or Nm ³	Th de P.C.B ⁸
Total annual		

⁸ P.C.B: It is a way of charging the fuel consumption by the supplying companies

Technical Sheet 23

3. Energy supplies

7. Audit on energy supplies

72. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in energy supplies:

1. Has a responsible been appointed to check the invoices for the water and energy supply?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

2. Are monthly water and energy meter readings taken?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

3. Is it verified that the invoiced amounts of water and energy are correct?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

4. Is the electricity supply contract reviewed annually?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

5. Is the energy consumption that takes place at night and on weekends known?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

6. If the contracted rate includes valley billing periods, is consumption planned to take advantage of its economic advantages?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

7. Is the power factor value continuously monitored?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

8. Have offers been requested from different diesel and LPG distributors?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

9. Have offers been requested from different electric energy trading companies?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

10. If you have more than one supply contract, have you considered the possibility of unifying them?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

11. Does the building belong to a diesel or LPG purchasing consortium?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

12. Do you try to avoid buying small quantities of diesel?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

13. In the purchase of diesel and LPG, is seasonal variation in prices considered?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

Technical Sheet 24

3. Energy supplies

8. Improvements in energy supplies

73. Improvements in the supply of electricity and / or fuels justified by energy efficiency, identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion		€	
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

More supply guarantee

High security

High salubrity

Less maintenance

More free space

High reliability

Others:

4. HEATING SYSTEM

Technical Sheet 25

4. Heating system

1. General characteristics of the heating system

74. The building has a heating system: Yes No

75. The heating system is:

- a. Exclusive to the building under study
- b. Centralized for the following buildings:

76. Heated area in the study building: %/Total, or m³

77. Main building heating system (indicate heat generating equipment):

Fuel boilers	Electric radiators or fan-convectors
Electric boilers	Electric accumulators
Electric heat pumps	Other:

78. Distribution system and / or emission of heat from the generation and terminal units

Air	Water or Steam	others
Air conditioners, ducts and diffusers; Autonomous conditioners; Hot air generators; Others:	Water radiators; Fan-coils or air heaters; Radiant floor or ceiling pipes; Others:	Electrical radiator/fan-convector; Electric accumulators; Electric radiant floor or ceiling; Window conditioners; Stoves (gas, kerosene, etc); Multi-split or VRV systems; Others:

Technical Sheet 26

4. Heating system

2. Heat generating equipment

79. Technical characteristics of the main heat equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipments				
Service(s)				
Installation location				
Nature of the equipment				
Energy used				
Type				
Carrier fluid				
Burner				
No. of stages				
Fuel flow (kg/s)	Max			
	Min			
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Useful power (kW)				
Absorbed (consumed) power (kW)				
Nominal yield (%)				
Stepping power				
Temperature of usage (°C)				
Temperature of departure (°C)				
Pressure of departure (Bar)				
Return temperature (°C)				
Return pressure (Bar)				
Operating regime				
Winter: number of months				
Hours/day of operation				
Observations				

80. Total thermal power installed in heat generating equipment:

kW

Technical Sheet 27

4. Heating system

3. Heat emitting equipment

81. Technical characteristics of the main heat emitting equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipment				
Zone(s)/Local				
Nature of the equipment				
Fluid				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Useful power (kW)				
Flow (Nm ³ /h)				
Input temperature (°C)				
Output temperature (°C)				
Observations				

82. Total thermal power installed in heat emitting equipment:

kW

4. Pumping equipment

83. Technical characteristics of the pumping equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipment				
Zone(s)/Local				
Installation location				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Power (kW)				
Flow (L/s)				
Rotation speed (rpm)				
Hours/day of operation				
Observations				

84. total installed power in pumping equipment:

kW

Technical Sheet 28

4. Heating system

5. Pipelines

85. Technical characteristics of the pipes:

Pipelines					
Use					
Material					
Class/Standard					
Thermal insulation type					
Exterior termination type					
Average fluid service temperature (°C)					
Working pressure					

6. Heating scheme(s)

86. Scheme(s) of the boiler room, fluid distribution, etc. of heating:

7. Heating maintenance

87. Maintenance operations carried out periodically in the heating installation:

There is no maintenance;

Only basic checks are performed;

There is a full maintenance contract;

Others:

Technical Sheet 29

4. Heating system

8. Heating regulation

88. Existing heating regulation systems:

Fully manual control
Thermostat for the entire system
Local or zone thermostat
Control unit programmable by external probe
Remote management or remote control

Programmable clock for the whole system
Chrono-thermostat for the entire system
Thermostat in each terminal unit
Computer centralized management
Others:

89. Control and regulation system control points:

DESCRIPTION	DI ⁹	AI ¹⁰	DO ¹¹	AO ¹²	SO ¹³	CT ¹⁴
Heated areas						
Average ambient temperature of the area						
Ambient relative humidity of the area						
Hot water production system						
Boiler start/stop command for heating support						
State/general alarm heating boilers						
Start/stop command for 2 primary hot water pumps						
State/alarm for 2 primary hot water pumps						
Lack of pressure / water signal in primary hot water circuit						
Water return temperature signal to boilers						
Boiler water outlet temperature signal						
Command to automatic hot water valves						
Limit automatic water valve regulation command						
Limit switches automatic hot water valves						
Secondary pumping and distribution circuits						
Hot water secondary pumps start / stop command						
Status / alarm secondary hot water pumps						
Reading hot water / circuit flow temperature						
Reading hot water / circuit return temperature						
Consumption meter						
General water meter						
Water supply meter to facilities						
General electric energy meter						
General gas supply meter						

⁹ DI: Digital input

¹⁰ AI: Analog input

¹¹ DO: Digital output

¹² AO: Analog output

¹³ SO: Suspension output

¹⁴ CT: Counter

Technical Sheet 30

4. Heating system

90. Storage conditions for heating (winter season):

Space	Temperature (°C)	Humidity (% HR)	Observations

9. Heating quality

91. The temperature is in general:

Adequate

Higher

Lower

92. Possible deficiencies in heating distribution and quality:

Heat is poorly distributed

The environment is excessively dry

The system is slow, it has a lot of inertia

The system is unreliable (many breakdowns)

There are sanitary problems

Others:

Technical Sheet 31

4. Heating system

10. Combustion analysis of fuel boilers

93. Results of the analysis of combustion and condition of chimneys of fuel boilers:

Designation					
frontal area (m ²)					
Posterior area (m ²)					
Lateral area (m ²)					
Boiler materials					
Chimney material					
Chimney surface temperature (°C)					
Smoke temperature (°C)					
Average frontal temperature (°C)					
Post average temperature (°C)					
Average lateral temperature (°C)					
Opacity Index					
Chimney draft (mm.c.a.)					
O ₂ concentration (% by volume)					
CO concentration (% by volume)					
NO _x concentration (% by volume)					
SO ₂ concentration (% by volume)					
CO ₂ concentration (% by volume)					
Air excess coefficient / norm (pu)					
Excess air coefficient / equipment (pu)					
Losses from unburned gases (%)					
Solid unburned losses (%)					
Sensitive heat losses in fumes (%)					
Radiation / convection losses (%)					
Combustion yield (%)					
Performance boiler / standard (%)					
Performance boiler / equipment (%)					
Performance boiler / calculations (%)					
General condition of the boiler					
General condition of the chimney					

Technical Sheet 32

4. Heating system

11. Measurements results of indoor winter conditions

94. Winter temperature and humidity measurement results:

Date and hour	Local	Activity	Measurements			
			Interior		Exterior	
			T(°C)	HR (%)	T(°C)	HR (%)

95. Results of other measurements of the heating system:

Date and hour	Parameter	Measurement conditions	Results

Technical Sheet 33

4. Heating system

96. Location of indoor winter conditions on the psychrometric diagram:

Technical Sheet 34

4. Heating system

12. Heating audit

97. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in heating:

- | | |
|---|--|
| <p>1. Is the operation of the boiler checked weekly?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>10. Is the correct functioning of the defrost thermostats of the heat pumps regularly checked?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>2. Is the Boiler Room adequately ventilated?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>11. Is there a program to clean radiators and change fan filters?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>3. Is there a leak detection procedure in place?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>12. Is the official maintenance service realizing an annual review of the boiler?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>4. In installations with several boilers, do some of them turn off in periods with milder weather conditions?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>13. Are all pipes, flanges, and valves insulated?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>5. Is the operation of several boilers in parallel sequenced?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>14. Does the heating and hot water supply come from different boilers?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>6. Is the ignition of the boiler piezoelectric or electronic?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>15. Is the boiler very oversized?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>7. When there is no heat demand in the areas to be heated, do the boilers work continuously?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>16. Is the actual yield of the boilers known?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>8. Are air radiators and diffusers free of obstacles?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>17. Is the heat recovered from the air expelled outside?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>9. Do staff use portable electric heaters without permission?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>18. Has the use of condensing boilers been considered?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |

Technical Sheet 35

4. Heating system

13. Heating improvements

98. Improvements in the heating system justified by energy efficiency, identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion	€		
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

5. REFRIGERATION SYSTEM

Technical Sheet 36

5. Refrigeration system

1. General characteristics of the cooling system

99. The building has a cooling system for the locals: Yes No
100. The cooling system is:
- a. Exclusive to the building under study
 - b. Centralized for the following buildings:
101. Refrigerated area in the building under study is: %/total or m²
102. General type of installation
- Individual equipment
Semi-centralized installation
Centralized installation

103. Main building cooling system (indicate cold generating equipment):

Electric chillers

Electric heat pumps

Others:

104. The cold generating machines are:

Air/Air

Air/Water

Water/Air

Water/Water

105. Cold distribution and emission system and terminal units:

Air	Water	Others
Air conditioners and diffusers	Fan coils	Window conditioners
Autonomous conditioners	Others:	Multi-split conditioners or VRV systems
Others:		Others:

Technical Sheet 37

5. Refrigeration system

2. Cold generating equipment

106. Technical characteristics of the main cold generation equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipments				
Installation location				
Nature of the equipment				
Energy used				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Useful power (kW)				
Absorbed (consumed) power (kW)				
Nominal COP				
Stepping power				
Temperature of usage (°C)				
Temperature of departure (°C)				
Pressure of departure (Bar)				
Return temperature (°C)				
Return pressure (Bar)				
Operating regime				
Summer: number of months				
Winter: number of months				
Observations				

107. Total thermal power installed in cold generating equipment:
kW

Technical Sheet 38

5. Refrigeration system

3. Cold emitting equipment

108. Technical characteristics of the main cold generation equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipment				
Installation location				
Nature of the equipment				
Fluid				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Useful power (kW)				
Flow (Nm ³ /h)				
Nominal COP				
Stepping power				
Input temperature(°C)				
Output temperature (°C)				
Observations				

109. Total thermal power installed in cold generating equipment:
kW

4. Refrigeration scheme(s)

110. Principles scheme(s) of, machine room, cooling etc.

Technical Sheet 39

5. Refrigeration system

5. Cooling maintenance

111. Maintenance operations carried out periodically in the refrigeration installation:

- There is no maintenance;
- Only basic checks are performed;
- There is a full maintenance contract;
- Others:

6. Refrigeration regulation

112. Existing refrigeration regulation systems:

- | | |
|---|---|
| Fully manual control | Programmable clock for the whole system |
| Thermostat for the entire system | Chrono-thermostat for the entire system |
| Local or zone thermostat | Thermostat in each terminal unit |
| Control unit programmable by external probe | Computer centralized management |
| Remote management or remote control | Others: |

113. Control and regulation system control points:

DESCRIPTION	DI ¹⁵	AI ¹⁶	DO ¹⁷	AO ¹⁸	SO ¹⁹	CT ²⁰
Heated areas						
Average ambient temperature of the area						
Ambient relative humidity of the area						
Cold production system						
Command start / stop cold generation equipment						
General status / alarm cold generating equipment						
Fluid return temperature signal						
Fluid flow temperature signal						
Consumption accounting						
General water meter						
Water supply meter to facilities						
General electric energy meter						

¹⁵ DI: Digital input

¹⁶ AI: Analog input

¹⁷ DO: Digital output

¹⁸ AO: Analog output

¹⁹ SO: Supervised output

²⁰ CT: Counter

Technical Sheet 40

5. Refrigeration system

114. Storage conditions for refrigeration (summer season):

Space	Temperature (°C)	Humidity (% HR)	Observations

7. Refrigeration quality

115. The temperature is in general:

Adequate

Higher

Lower

116. Possible deficiencies in cooling distribution and quality:

Cold is poorly distributed

The environment is excessively dry

The system is slow, it has a lot of inertia

The system is unreliable (many breakdowns)

There are sanitary problems

Others:

8. Measurement results of indoor conditions in summer

117. Summer temperature and humidity measurement results:

Date and hour	Local	Activity	Measurements			
			Interior		Exterior	
			T(°C)	HR (%)	T(°C)	HR (%)

Technical Sheet 41

5. Refrigeration system

118. Refrigeration system measurement results:

Date and hour	Parameter	Measurement conditions	Results

119. Location of indoor summer conditions on the psychrometric diagram:

Technical Sheet 42

5. Refrigeration system

9. Refrigeration audit

120. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in refrigeration:

- | | |
|--|---|
| <p>1. Is a weekly check of the chiller room planned?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>9. Does the official maintenance service check the chillers annually?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>2. Are you set up a method for detecting leaks or coolant leaks?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>10. Are the air distribution ducts insulated?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>3. In installations with several chillers, are these switched off successively as the weather conditions moderate?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>11. Are all pipes, flanges and valves insulated in the refrigeration circuit?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>4. Do the chillers operate continuously when there is no demand for cold in the areas to be conditioned?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>12. Is the cold production machinery oversized?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>5. Are fan coils and air diffusers free of obstacles?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>13. Is the power of the chillers fractionated?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>6. Do staff use portable “penguins” without authorization when there is a central air conditioning system?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>14. Is the air conditioning of special premises separated from the rest of the rooms?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>7. Are there uncontrolled heat sources in the conditioned rooms?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>15. Is free air cooling taken advantage of at halftime?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>8. Is there a cleaning program to maintain the air ducts and change the dirty filters of the fan-coils?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | |

Technical Sheet 43

5. Refrigeration system

10. Cooling system improvements

121. Improvements in the refrigeration system justified by energy efficiency identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion		€	
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

122. Other advantages of this improvement:

More comfort

High security

High salubrity

Best distributed cold

High reliability

Others:

6. VENTILATION SYSTEM

Technical Sheet 44

6. Ventilation system

1. General characteristics of the ventilation system

- | | | Yes | No |
|-------------|--|-----|----|
| 123. | The building has a ventilation system: | | |
| 124. | The ventilation system is: | | |
| | a. Exclusive to the building under study | | |
| | b. Centralized for the following buildings: | | |
| 125. | Independence of the ventilation system: | | |
| | It is integrated into the heating system | | |
| | It is integrated into the air conditioning system | | |
| | It is an independent system | | |
| 126. | Type of ventilation: | | |
| | Mechanics | | |
| | with mechanical admission | | |
| | with mechanical extraction | | |
| | balanced | | |
| | natural | | |
| | Hybrid | | |
| 127. | Nature of the building's ventilation system (indicate basic form of air renewal): | | |
| | Forced supply of the cooling air by means of supply fans | | |
| | Forced extraction of stale air using exhaust fans | | |
| | Extraction of stale air by natural draft using deck extractors | | |

Technical Sheet 45

6. Ventilation system

128. Air circulation:

Air circulates from dry to wet rooms

129. Admission:

There are openings for admission in:

Dining rooms

Bedrooms

Living rooms

Others

Are directly connected to the outside

Are communicated through an intake duct

The aerators are at a distance from the ground of

Class and use of carpentry as intake (admission) openings

Carpentry class	Use of admission openings
Class 0	Opening joints Other
Class 1	Opening joints Other
Class 2	Openings equipped with aerators Fixed carpentry openings Others
Class 3	Openings equipped with aerators Fixed carpentry openings Others
Class 4	Openings equipped with aerators Fixed carpentry openings Others

Technical Sheet 46

6. Ventilation system

130. Extraction:

There are extraction openings in:

toilets

kitchens

others

Are directly connected to the outside

Are connected to extraction ducts

Are at a distance from the ceiling of

Are at a distance from any corner to vertical corner of

The extraction ducts are not shared with other uses premises except with the storage rooms

In premises with compartmentalized extraction, indicate the situation of:

Passage openings

Extraction opening

131. Passage:

The partitions located between the premises with admission and the premises with extraction have access openings

The premises with various uses have in each area destined for a different use the corresponding openings

Technical Sheet 47

6. Ventilation system

2. Ventilation equipment

132. Technical characteristics of the main ventilation equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipment				
Service(s)				
Installation location				
Nature of the equipment				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Total air flow (m ³ /h)				
Refreshment air flow (m ³ /h)				
Useful power (kW)				
Absorbed (consumed) power (kW)				
Nominal yield (%)				
Air filter				
Observations				

133. Total capacity of air renewal
m³/h

134. Total thermal power installed in air renewal equipment
kW

Technical Sheet 48

6. Ventilation system

135. Technical characteristics of the intake openings:

OPENINGS				
Location				
Identification				
Type				
Communication with outside				
Effective area dimensions (cm ²)				
Type of aerator				
Nominal flow (L/s)				
Observations				

136. Technical characteristics of the ducts:

DUCTS				
Location				
Identification				
Use				
Longitude (m)				
Dimensions (cm * cm)				
Area (m ²)				
Flow (L/s)				
Shooting class				
Observations				

Technical Sheet 49

6. Ventilation system

3. Ventilation quality

137. Possible deficiencies in ventilation distribution and quality:

Air velocity is excessive	The system is noisy
Poor ambient air quality	It is poorly regulated
Causes health problems	The system is unreliable, has breakdowns
Others:	

138. Indoor air quality category:

It is unknown

IDA 1- optimum quality air

IDA 2 - good quality air

IDA 3 - medium quality air

IDA 4 - low quality air

139. Outdoor air quality:

It is unknown

ODA 1- pure air that may temporarily contain solid particles

ODA 2 - air with high concentrations of particles

ODA 3 - air with high concentrations of gaseous pollutants

ODA 4 - air with high concentrations of gaseous and particulate pollutants

ODA 5 - air with very high concentrations of gaseous and particulate pollutants

140. Extraction air:

It is unknown

AE 1- low level of pollution

AE 2 - moderate level of pollution

AE 3 - high level of pollution

AE 4 - very high level of pollution

Technical Sheet 50

6. Ventilation system

4. Ventilation schemes

141. Principle diagram of machine room ventilation, etc.

5. Measurement results of ventilation conditions

142. Measurement results for each of the premises:

Premise (local)	
Activity	
No. of occupants	
Local longitude (m)	
Local width (m)	
Local height (m)	
Minimum required ventilation flow (L/s)	
Measured ventilation flow (L/s)	
Observations	

Technical Sheet 51

6. Ventilation system

6. Maintenance of ventilation

143. Maintenance operations carried out periodically in the ventilation installation:

There is no maintenance

Filters are cleaned and / or replaced periodically

Ducts, exchangers, boxes, etc. are periodically cleaned.

There is a full maintenance contract

Others:

144. The maintenance plan contains the following operations:

Installation element	Operation	Frequency	Observations
Ducts	Cleaning Checking the apparent tightness		
Opening	Cleaning		
Hybrid, mechanical and extractor vacuum cleaners	Cleaning Functionality status review		
Filters	Status review Cleaning or replacement		
Control systems	Review of the status of your automation		

Technical Sheet 52

6. Ventilation system

7. Ventilation audit

145. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in ventilation

1. Are unnecessary fans turned off?

Yes

No

2. Are individual fans used in an unauthorized way?

Yes

No

3. Are natural ventilation systems used?

Yes

No

4. Is the operating time of the exhaust fans in premises such as toilets and kitchens controlled?

Yes

No

5. Is the operating time of garage fans controlled?

Yes

No

6. Are extractors equipped with automatic shutters?

Yes

No

7. Have you checked the cleanliness of the inside ventilation ducts?

Yes

No

8. Has it been verified that the ventilation flows are not excessive?

Yes

No

9. Is air recirculation planned?

Yes

No

Technical Sheet 53

6. Ventilation system

146. Improvements in the ventilation system justified by energy efficiency identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion	€		
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

7. SANITATRY HOT WATER SYSTEM (DHW)

Technical Sheet 54

7. Sanitary hot water system

1. General characteristics of the DHW system

147. The building has some DHW production system: Yes No

148. DHW's production system is:

- a. Exclusive to the building under study
- b. Centralized for the following buildings:

149. Maximum DHW demand covered: L/ h, or L/ day at °C

150. Services served by the DHW:

Laundries and sinks

Showers

Washing machines

heated swimming pools

Others:

151. DHW main production system (primary heating form):

Electric thermo(s) accumulator(s)

Instant heater for combustible ()

Domestic mixed boilers for combustible ()

Central boilers for combustible () shared with heating

Central boilers for combustible () with exclusive dedication

Others:

2. Production, accumulation and distribution of DHW

152. DHW production system (form of secondary heating):

Plate heat exchanger

Inter-accumulator tank

Exchanger incorporated (mixed boiler)

Direct production (electric, ac., Etc.)

153. DHW distribution system from production to point of consumption:

Direct from thermos, tank or boiler

Through recirculation circuit

Technical Sheet 55

7. Sanitary hot water system

154. Characteristics of the DHW heating equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipment				
Service(s)				
Nature of the equipment				
Energy used				
Type				
Burner				
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Useful power (kW)				
Absorbed (consumed) power (kW)				
Nominal yield (%)				
Stepping power				
Temperature of usage (°C)				
Temperature of departure (°C)				
Pressure of departure (Bar)				
Return temperature (°C)				
Return pressure (Bar)				
Observations				

155. Characteristics of the DHW accumulation tanks:

Designation				
No. of equal equipment				
Service(s)				
Maximum capacity (l)				
Average temperature (°C)				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Materials				
Year of manufacture				
Observations				

Technical Sheet 56

7. Sanitary hot water system

3. DHW schemes:

156. Principle scheme(s) of machines room...etc, of DHW:

4. DHW maintenance

157. Maintenance operations carried out periodically at the DHW facility:

There is no maintenance;

Only basic checks are performed;

There is a full maintenance contract;

Others:

Technical Sheet 57

7. Sanitary hot water system

5. DHW regulation

158. Forms of regulation of the production of DHW:

Control by manual mixing	Control over instantaneous production temperature
Accumulation temperature probe	Control over output temperature of the tank
Timed shower buttons	thermostatic Faucet
Zone thermostatic valves	Centralized computer control
Remote management or remote control	Others:

159. DHW setpoint conditions:

Point	setpoint temperature (°C)		Observations
	Winter	Summer	

6. DHW quality

160. The temperature of DHW is in general:

Adequate

Higher

Lower

161. Possible deficiencies in DHW distribution and quality:

The DHW is poorly distributed	Flow and/or temperature oscillations
Capacity is low (runs out quickly)	The system is unreliable (breakdowns)
The A.C. S. takes time to reach the point of consumption	Others:

Technical Sheet 58

7. Sanitary hot water system

7. DHW audit

162. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in DHW:

1. Are the staff careless and leave taps badly closed?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
2. Are leaky faucets repaired immediately?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
3. Are pipes periodically checked for leaks?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
4. Is the hot water distribution temperature excessive?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
5. Is hot water used where cold water is equally effective?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
6. During vacation periods, do all water heating systems turn off?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
7. Are the equipment that controls the DHW production system correctly programmed?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
8. Is there a non-return valve in the pipeline connecting the boiler to the distribution tank or to the collector?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
9. When a large number of storage tanks are available, has their use been studied from the point of view of energy efficiency?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
10. Are the storage tanks isolated?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

Technical Sheet 59

7. Sanitary hot water system

161. Questions about energy efficiency in the DHW (continued)

11. And are the hot water distribution pipes insulated?
- Yes** **No**
12. Are programmer clocks used to control the period of operation of the intercoms?
- Yes** **No**
13. Is there control over the operating time of the circulation pumps?
- Yes** **No**
14. Do they shut all taps correctly?
- Yes** **No**
15. Are flow reducers used in faucets for sinks, bidets, sinks and showers?
- Yes** **No**
16. In dual-control showers, has the possibility of installing flow switches been studied?
- Yes** **No**
17. In the men's toilets, do the urinals have flowmeters?
- Yes** **No**
18. Can the flow of the tanks be regulated?
- Yes** **No**
19. Are all hoses closed after use?
- Yes** **No**
20. Is the water heated near the consumption point?
- Yes** **No**
21. Have you considered the option of exchanging the water tank for an exchanger?
- Yes** **No**

Technical Sheet 60

7. Sanitary hot water system

8. DHW installation improvements

162. Improvements in the installation of DHW justified by energy efficiency identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion	€		
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

More comfort

Higher salubrity

Higher security

Higher reliability

Faster

Others:

8. INSTALLATION OF THERMAL SOLAR ENERGY

Technical Sheet 61

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

1. General characteristics of solar thermal energy installation

163. The building has thermal solar energy: Yes No
164. The thermal solar energy system is:
- a. Exclusive to the building under study
 - b. Centralized for the following buildings:
165. The main end uses of solar thermal are:
- | DHW | Heated pool | Heating |
|--|--------------|----------------|
| 166. Total effective area of the installation: | | m ² |
| 167. Installation location: | | |
| General | | |
| Overlap | | |
| Architectural integration | | |
| 168. Reference temperature of DHW demand: | | °C |
| 169. Auxiliary support system: | | |
| General | Joule effect | |
| Diesel | | |
| Propane | | |
| Natural Gas | | |
| Others: | | |
170. General data of the DHW demand:

No. of consumptions	
Specific consumption (L/ day for ref. unit)	
Demand reference at 60 °C DHW (L/day)	
Accumulation volume (L)	

Technical Sheet 62

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

171. Minimum required solar contribution: %
 172. Solar contribution of the system:

Month	DHW demand (L)	Energy demand (kWh)	Solar contribution (kWh)	Solar contribution/demand * 100 (%)
January				
February				
March				
April				
May				
June				
July				
August				
September				
October				
November				
December				
Total				

2. Scheme of the solar thermal installation

Technical Sheet 63

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

3. absorption system

173. Scheme of the solar thermal installation:

No. of solar collectors			
Dimensions (A*L, (m))			
Effective collector area (m²)			
Collector efficiency factor			
Global loss coefficient (W/m² °C)			
Orientation (°)			
Losses	For orientation or inclination (%)		
	for shading (%)		
	Total (%)		
State			
Corrosion			
Supports			
Hydraulic piping			
Circulating fluid			
Temperatures	Collector	Input	Output

Technical Sheet 64

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

174. Technical characteristics of solar collectors:

Brand	
Model	
Type	
Cover	
Effective collector area (m²)	
Collector efficiency factor	
Global loss coefficient (W/m² °C)	

4. Connection scheme of solar collectors:

Technical Sheet 65

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

5. Hydraulic circuit

175. Characteristics of the primary circuit:

Location		
Longitude (m)		
Diameter (m)		
Isolations		
Leaks		
Corrosions		
Flows (L/s)		
Temperatures (°C)		
Pump	Nominal flow (L/s)	
	Power (kW)	
	Location	
Valves	Type	
	Placement	
Other auxiliaries		
Observations		

176. Characteristics of the secondary circuit:

Location		
Longitude (m)		
Diameter (m)		
Isolations		
Leaks		
Corrosions		
Flows (L/s)		
Temperatures (°C)		
Pump	Nominal flow (L/s)	
	Power (kW)	
	Location	
Valves	Type	
	Placement	
Other auxiliaries		
Observations		

Technical Sheet 66

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

6. Exchange system

177. Technical characteristics of the exchanger:

Brand				
Model				
Number				
Location				
Type				
Minimal power (kW)				
Exchange area				
Nominal flows (L/h)	Collector side		Tank side	
Maximum flows (L/h)	Collector side		Tank side	
Isolations	Type			
	Thickness			
	State			
Temperatures (°C)	Collector input		Collector output	
	Tank input		Tank output	
Union of probes				
State				
Leaks				
Corrosions				
Observations				

Technical Sheet 67

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

7. Accumulation system

178. Technical characteristics of the exchanger:

Brand				
Model				
Location				
Geometry				
Volume (L)				
Isolations	Type			
	Thickness			
	State			
Temperatures (°C)	Exchanger input		Exchanger output	
	Boiler /consumption input		Boiler /consumption output	
Union of probes				
State				
Leaks				
Corrosions				
Observations				

Technical Sheet 68

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

8. Auxiliary conventional power system

179. Technical characteristics of the conventional auxiliary power system:

Type	
Brand	
Model	
Power	
Combustible	
Consumption (kWh)	
Operating hours	
State	
Setpoint temperature	
Drive	
Hydraulic connection	
Other features	
Observations	

9. Control and measurement systems

180. Technical characteristics of the control system:

Type	
Functioning	
Setpoint	
Problems detected	
Observations	

181. Measurement system features:

The solar thermal measurement system has a measurement system: Yes No

The measurement system controls the following variables:

Input temperature of the cold-water network

Solar storage outlet temperature

Flow of cold-water network

The measurement system provides the accumulated thermal solar energy: Yes No

Technical Sheet 69

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

10. Maintenance of the solar thermal energy system

182. Maintenance operations carried out periodically in the solar thermal energy installation:

There is no maintenance

Only basic checks are performed

A surveillance plan exists and is applied

A maintenance plan exists and is applied

183. The surveillance plan contains the following operations:

Installation element	Operation	Frequency
Collectors	Crystal Cleaning Observation of condensations on crystals Visual inspection of joint condition Visual inspection of absorber Visual inspection of the structure	
Primary circuit	Visual inspection of piping, insulation and filling system Emptying the air from the manual drain bottle	
Secondary circuit	Visual inspection of the thermometer Visual inspection of pipe and insulation Purged sludge accumulation bottom tank	

Technical Sheet 70

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

184. The maintenance plan contains the following operations:

Installation element	Operation	Frequency
Collectors	Visual inspection of differences on original Visual inspection of differences between collectors	
Crystals	Visual inspection of condensation and dirt	
Joints	Visual inspection cracks and deformations	
Absorber	Visual inspection for corrosion and deformation	
Case	Visual inspection for deficiencies, oscillations, breathing windows	
Connections	Visual inspection for leaks	
Structure	Visual inspection degradation, corrosion starts, tighten screws	
Tank	Presence of sludge in the bottom	
Sacrificial anodes	Wear check	
Printed current anodes	Proof of proper operation	
Insulation	Moisture free check	
Plate exchanger	Efficiency and performance control Cleaning	
Coil exchanger	Efficiency and performance control Cleaning	
Coolant fluid	Density and PH check	
Watertightness	Carry out a pressure test	
Exterior insulation	Visual inspection degradation protection joints and absence of moisture	
Interior insulation	Visual inspection of joints and absence of moisture	
Automatic drain	Correct operation and cleaning	
Manual drain	Empty the air from the bottle	
Pump	Watertightness	
Closed expansion vessel	Pressure check	
Open expansion vessel	Level check	
Filling system	Operating performance test	
Cut valve	Check operation of performances (open and close) to avoid jamming	
Security valve	Operating performance test	
Electric board	Always check tightly closed to avoid dust entry	
Differential control	Operating performance test	
Thermostat	Operating performance test	
Measurement system verification	Operating performance test	
Auxiliary system	Operating performance test	
Temperature probes	Operating performance test	

Technical Sheet 71

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

11. Audit of the solar thermal energy system

185. Answer the following questions about the energy efficiency of the solar thermal energy installation:

1. Do collectors look deteriorated or very dirty?

Yes

No

2. Does the hydraulic circuit observe a proper state of isolation?

Yes

No

3. Is the hydraulic circuit properly balanced?

Yes

No

4. Are there any leaks?

Yes

No

5. Are the angle and orientation of the collector optimal?

Yes

No

6. Does the DHW production auxiliary support system work only when needed?

Yes

No

7. Is there any corrosion?

Yes

No

Technical Sheet 72

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

12. Improvements in the installation of solar thermal energy

186. Improvements in the installation of solar thermal energy justified by energy efficiency identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion		€	
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

9. COGENERATION FACILITY

Technical Sheet 73

9. Cogeneration facility

1. General characteristics of the plant

187. The building has a cogeneration facility: Yes No
188. General plant data:

Year of construction	
No. of operating hours	
Performing Overhaul (year, number of hours)	
Promoter, engineering and beneficiaries or partners of the plant	
Operation and management modality	
Grid connection	

2. Characteristics of the cogeneration group

189. Technical characteristics of the cogeneration group:

Group characteristics	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type 4
Turbine (T) or alternate combustion engine (MCI)				
Brand and model				
Combustible (diesel, gas, biogas...)				
Combustible consumption (kW)				
Nominal electrical power (kW)				
Electrical yield				
Heat dissipated in cooling circuit only (MCI) (kW)				
Heat in exhaust gases (kW)				
Sum of useful heat (kW)				
Alternator: number of poles, voltage and frequency				
Number of equal motor-generator groups				

Technical Sheet 74

9. Cogeneration facility

3. Characteristics of the electrical installation

190. Grid connection characteristics:

The energy produced through the common transformer is exported, billed for the difference in meters.

The energy produced is exported through an independent transformer for cogeneration.

The energy produced in low voltage is exported, through a connection point authorized by the electrical distribution company.

The energy produced is self-consumed, injecting into the general low voltage panel.

Other options:

191. Characteristics of major equipment:

Transformer	
Power (kW)	
Transformer voltage (V)	
Common or independent (C/I)	
Measurement counter (Yes/No)	
Protection and measurement	
Brand and model of the counter	
Telemetry (Yes/No)	
Protection cells	
Alternator	
Mechanical power on axis (kW)	
Nominal power on alternator terminals (kVA)	
Effective power at $\cos \varphi = 0.8$	
Effective power at $\cos \varphi = 1$	
Rotation speed (rpm)	
Pole pairs	
Yield at $\cos \varphi = 0.8$	
Yield at $\cos \varphi = 1$	
Number of phases	
Voltage (V)	
Frequency	

Technical Sheet 75

9. Cogeneration facility

192. Electrical scheme of the system:

4. Characteristics of the mechanical installation

193. Pumping groups:

Pumping groups				
No. of equal equipment				
Installation location				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of production				
Power (kW)				
Flow (L/s)				
Rotation speed (rpm)				
Operation (hours/day)				
Observations				

194. Pipelines:

Pipelines				
Use				
Material				
Class/norm				
Thermal insulation type				
Exterior insulation type				
Average fluid service temperature (°C)				
Work pressure				

Technical Sheet 76

9. Cogeneration facility

195. Plate exchangers:

Exchanger				
No. of equal equipment				
Installation location				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of production				
Power (kW)				
Input/output temperature 1st (°C)				
Input/output temperature 2nd (°C)				
Flows 1st/2nd (m ³ /h)				
Observations				

196. Smoke recovery boilers:

boiler				
No. of equal equipment				
Installation location				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of production				
Nominal yield				
Smoke flow (m ³ /h)				
Power (kW)				
Smoke input/output temperature (°C)				
Water/steam input/output temperature (°C)				
Water/steam flow (m ³ /h)				
Observations				

Technical Sheet 77

9. Cogeneration facility

197. Absorption chillers:

Chiller				
No. of equal equipment				
Installation location				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of production				
Outlet temperature of cooled water (°C)				
Flow (m ³)				
Cooling power (kW)				
Intlet temperature of cooled water (°C)				
Tower outlet temperature (°C)				
Tower water flow (m ³ /h)				
Return water inlet temperature (°C)				
Return water outlet temperature (°C)				
Hot water inlet temperature (°C)				
Hot water outlet temperature (°C)				
Flow (L/s)				
Electric consumption (kVA)				
Observations				

198. Installation schematic:

Technical Sheet 78

9. Cogeneration facility

5. Operating parameters

199. Annual parameters obtained by the system:

Electric power	
Exported electrical energy (kWh/year)	
Self-consumed electric energy (kWh/year)	
Annual electricity production (E) (kWh/year)	
Seasonal electrical yield	
Instantaneous electrical yield (measured by the auditor)	
Heat	
Annual production of useful heat (V) (kWh/year)	
Seasonal thermal yield	
Instantaneous thermal yield (measured by the auditor)	
combustible	
Annual combustible consumption (Q) (kWh/year)	
Availability	
Annual availability of the plant (h/year)	

200. Calculation of equivalent electrical yield:

	kWh/year
Annual electricity production (E)	
Annual production of useful heat (V)	
Annual combustible consumption (Q)	

Technical Sheet 79

9. Cogeneration facility

201. Measurement results of the most important parameters:

Residual heat measurement. Recovery boiler	Smokes inlet temperature (°C)			
	Smokes outlet temperature (°C)			
	Gas flow (kg/h)			
Measurement of heat transfer in plate exchangers	Secondary water inlet temperature (°C)			
	Secondary water outlet temperature (°C)			
	secondary water flow (m ³ /h)			
Electricity	Electric power produced, measured at generator terminals (kWh)			
	Electric energy produced, measured in the central bars (kWh)			

202. Results of measurements of other significant parameters of cogeneration:

Date/hour	Parameter	Measured conditions	Results

Technical Sheet 80**9. Cogeneration facility****203. Thermography realized:**

Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification
Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification

204. Comments:**205. Observations:**

Technical Sheet 81

9. Cogeneration facility

6. Maintenance of the cogeneration system

206. Maintenance operations carried out periodically at the cogeneration facility:

There is no maintenance

Only basic checks are performed

There is an operation and surveillance service with a validity period of:

There is a remote management system and automatic fault report with an average intervention time of:

There is a corrective maintenance service

There is a comprehensive maintenance service (preventive + corrective -including in this the cost of the pieces)

Maintenance price: € /kWh generated

207. Maintenance plan:

A maintenance plan for the cogeneration facility exists and is applied

The maintenance plan is integrated together with the building

The maintenance plan is carried out by the same company that develops the maintenance of the building

The plan is attached within the audit

Technical Sheet 82

9. Cogeneration facility

7. Cogeneration system audit

208. Answer the following questions about the energy efficiency of the cogeneration installation:

1. Is the operation of the motor-generator or turbine group reviewed weekly?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
2. Is the condition of the recovery boiler (or exchanger) analysed?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
3. Has the possibility of producing cold with an absorption machine been analysed?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
4. Is all available heat used?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
5. Is the combustible supply system regularly checked?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
6. Is the maintenance work of the motor-generator set (or turbine) carried out regularly according to the manufacturer's guidelines?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
7. Are thermographic inspections carried out to analyse the insulation status of equipment, valves and distribution networks?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
8. Is combustion analysis performed?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
9. Is there oversizing of equipment?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
10. Is reactive energy regulated by capacitor banks?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
11. If electric energy is self-consumed, has the possibility of exporting energy under the special regime of electric energy producers been analysed?

Yes	No
------------	-----------
12. Is the cogeneration room properly ventilated?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

Technical Sheet 83

9. Cogeneration facility

8. Improvements in the cogeneration installation

209. Improvements in the cogeneration facility justified by energy efficiency identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion	€		
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

10.PHOTOVOLTAIC SOLAR ENERGY SYSTEM

Technical Sheet 84

10. Photovoltaic solar energy system

1. General characteristics of the photovoltaic solar energy installation

- 210.** The building has a photovoltaic solar installation: Yes No
- 211.** The photovoltaic solar energy production system is:
- a. Exclusive to the building under study
 - b. Centralized for the following buildings:
- 212.** The electrical energy produced is used to:
- | | self use | Grid supply |
|---|--------------------------|---|
| 213. Total surface of the installation | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> m ² |
| 214. Peak power of the installation | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> kW |
| 215. Minimum power required | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> kW |
| 216. Installation location: | | |
| General | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| Overlap | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| Architectural integration | <input type="checkbox"/> | |

2. Diagram of the photovoltaic solar installation

Technical Sheet 85

10. Photovoltaic solar energy system

3. Photovoltaic generator system

217. General characteristics of the photovoltaic solar energy system:

No. of modules		
Dimensions (m)		
Total effective area (m ²)		
Peak power (kW)		
Inclination (°)		
Orientation		
Losses	By orientation and inclination	
	By shading (%)	
	Total (%)	
General state		
Corrosions		
supports		

218. Technical characteristics of the collector:

Brand	
Model	
Type	
Effective collector area (m ²)	
Nominal power (kW)	
Yield	

Technical Sheet 86

10. Photovoltaic solar energy system

4. Inverter

219. Technical characteristics of the inverter:

Brand	
Model	
Type	
No. of inverters	
Total nominal power (kW)	
Nominal power of the inverter (kW)	

5. Maintenance of the photovoltaic solar energy system

220. Maintenance operations carried out periodically in the solar thermal energy installation:

There is no maintenance

Only basic checks are performed

A surveillance plan exists and is applied

A maintenance plan exists and is applied

221. Technical characteristics of the control system:

Electrical protections checking

Module status check: checking of the situation with respect to the original project and checking of the protection status

Inverter status check: operation, signalling lamps, alarms, etc.

Checking of the mechanical condition of cables and terminals, plates, transformers, fans / extractors, unions, retightening and cleaning

Technical Sheet 87

10. Photovoltaic solar energy system

6. Audit of the photovoltaic solar energy system

222. Answer the following questions about the energy efficiency of the photovoltaic solar energy installation:

1. Are the collectors look deteriorated or very dirty?

Yes

No

2. Is the angle and orientation of the collectors optimal?

Yes

No

3. Is there any corrosion?

Yes

No

7. Improvements in the installation of photovoltaic solar energy

223. Improvements in the installation of photovoltaic solar energy justified by energy efficiency identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion		€	
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

11.CONCLUSION

Technical Sheet 88

11. Conclusions

1. Summary of improvements

224. Summary of the improvements justified by energy efficiency, identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Area		Construction Features	Energy supplies	Heating system	Refrigeration system	Ventilation system
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity				
		Unit				
		(%)				
	Combustible	Quantity				
		Unit				
		(%)				
Total economic savings		€/year				
Total inversion		€				
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)						
Observations						

Technical Sheet 89

11. Conclusions

224. Summary of the improvements justified by energy efficiency, identified and evaluated technically and economically (continued):

Area			Sanitary hot water system	Installation of thermal solar energy	Cogeneration facility	Photovoltaic solar energy system	Total
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity					
		Unit					
		(%)					
	Combustible	Quantity					
		Unit					
		(%)					
Total economic savings		€/year					
Total inversion		€					
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)							
Observations							

Technical Sheet 92

11. Conclusions

4. General observations of the auditor

CONCLUSION

The theme proposed as part of my final master's project was to develop an energy audit procedure in the hotel sector in Morocco in order to assess the performance of equipment in a more precise and reliable way.

The first section was dedicated to present the tourism sector in Morocco and the different types of existing accommodation, more specifically hotels.

Then, in the second section, we became aware of the methodology and the importance of the energy audit and constituent parts, and the appropriate measurement devices used during the process was defined.

The third section was devoted to the application of the energy audit on a real case study of a hotel based in the city of Casablanca.

Finally, we conclude that the energy audit is fundamental for the hotel sector, which constitutes one of the pillars of the economy in Morocco, because it makes it possible to control the proper functioning of the installations and subsequently to control and minimize the energy bill while providing better comfort to customers during their stay, thus helping to preserve the environment by remedying any possible malfunction in time.

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CASE STUDY – Hotel Casablanca

0. GENERAL DATA OF THE ENERGY AUDIT

Technical Sheet 1

0. General data of the energy audit

Date:

1. Audit number:
2. Total number of buildings that is independently studied in any of the sections:
3. Number and name of each of the buildings that is independently studied:

N°	Designation/Name	N°	Designation/Name
00		05	
01		06	
02		07	
03		08	
04		09	

4. Number of times each section and buildings considered are completed:

Section						N°
0. General data of the energy audit	00 (All)					01
1. General Building data						
2. Construction Features						
3. Energy Supplies						
4. Lighting						
5. Heating System						
6. Refrigeration System						
7. Ventilation System						
8. DHW ¹ system						
9. Solar Thermal Energy Installation						
10. Engines						
11. Cogeneration Facility						
12. Other Energy Equipment						
13. Solar PV ² Energy Installation						
14. Signalling and Control Integration						
15. Concluding Remarks	00 (All)					01

5. Author:
6. Company:
7. Signature and stamp:

¹ DHW: Domestic Hot Water

² PV: Photovoltaic

1. GENERAL BUILDING DATA

Technical Sheet 2

1. General Building data

1. Identification and location

8. Building name:

9. Company:

10. Tax Identification Code (IF):

Website:

11. Purpose:

12. Street or square:

No.:

13. Zip Code:

Location:

14. District:

2. Contact person

15. Name:

16. Position:

17. Mobile phone:

Fax:

18. E-mail:

Technical Sheet 3

1. General Building data

3. Operating system

19. Maximum building capacity: persons.

20. Description of the most common tasks in the building:

Task	Description

21. Hours, days of the week and occupation for the most common tasks:

Season of the year	From: To:	From: To:	From: To:	From: To:	From: To:	From: To:
Rates						
Hours/Month						
Hours/Season						
Hours/Year						

22. Months in which the building is almost empty (unoccupied) for 15 or more days:

January	February	March	April	May	June
July	August	September	October	November	December

2. CONSTRUCTION FEATURES

Technical Sheet 4

2. Construction Features

1. Nature, location and age of the building

23. Building type:

Conventional

Monumental

Listed

24. Location:

Exempt between buildings

Between party walls

Totally isolated

25. Environment:

Urban

Rural

Isolated

26. Approximate year of construction:

27. Years of permanence in the building manager:

28. Years since the last major construction reform:

29. Nature of the former:

30. Are you planning to carry out any modification, reform or rehabilitation of the building?

Yes

No

31. Are you planning to carry out any modification, reform or rehabilitation of the building enclosures?

Yes

No

32. If so, what percentage of the total would the reform cover?

Technical Sheet 5

2. Construction Features

33. Energy rating obtained by the building:

Energy rating	In project	Final construction
Dwelling 1		
Dwelling 2		
Dwelling 3		
Dwelling 4		
Dwelling 5		
Dwelling 6		
Dwelling 7		
Dwelling 8		
Dwelling 9		
Dwelling 10		
Building		

Technical Sheet 6

2. Construction Features

2. Surfaces and heights

34. Number of floors:

Above ground:

Below ground:

35. Useful and/or built areas and free height by floors:

Floor	Area (m ²)		Height (m)	Volume (m ³)		Floor	Area (m ²)		Height (m)	Volume (m ³)	
	Built	Used		Built	Used		Built	Used		Built	Used

36. Total areas: built/useful:

m²/

m²

37. Total volumes: built/useful:

m³/

m³

3. Basic scheme(s) of the building

38. Sketch(s) of floor(s) and/or elevation(s):

Technical Sheet 7

2. Construction Features

4. Data collection of walls, floors, roofs and skylights

39. Characteristics of walls in contact with the ground, the exterior or with non-habitable spaces

Type	Insulating layer	Description

40. Sketches of type walls:

Technical Sheet 8

2. Construction Features

41. Characteristics of soils in contact with the ground or with non-habitable spaces:

Type	Insulating layer	Description

42. Sketch of type soils:

Technical Sheet 9

2. Construction Features

43. Characteristics of roofs in contact with the ground or with non-habitable spaces:

Type	Insulating layer	Description

44. Sketch of type covers:

Technical Sheet 10

2. Construction Features

45. Characteristics of openings and skylights in contact with the ground or with non-habitable spaces:

Type	Insulating layer	Description

46. Sketch of holes and type skylights:

Technical Sheet 11

2. Construction Features

- Measurements to be taken: thermography of walls, floors, roofs and skylights

47. Thermography carried out to walls:

Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification
Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification

48. Comments:

49. Observations:

Technical Sheet 12

2. Construction Features

50. Thermography carried out on soils:

Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification
Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification

51. Comments:

52. Observations:

Technical Sheet 13

2. Construction Features

53. Thermography carried out on roofs:

Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification
Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification

54. Comments:

55. Observations:

Technical Sheet 14

2. Construction Features

56. Thermography carried out on holes and skylights:

Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification
Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification

57. Comments:

58. Observations:

Technical Sheet 15

2. Construction Features

5. Audit on constructive aspects

59. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in construction:

1. Have you observed the appearance of damp on walls or ceilings?

Yes

No

2. Do doors and windows close when the heating or air conditioning system is on?

Yes

No

3. In summer, are the awnings lowered or are the curtains drawn of the windows located on the facades facing south or west?

Yes

No

4. Is it scheduled a periodic review of doors and windows?

Yes

No

5. Are there drafts from chimneys, air ducts or ventilation holes?

Yes

No

6. Are all unheated lofts and spaces under roofs insulated?

Yes

No

7. Are doors and windows sealed?

Yes

No

8. Do the door locks work correctly?

Yes

No

9. Are heated and unheated spaces properly separated?

Yes

No

10. Are all the air chambers insulated from the facade walls?

Yes

No

Technical Sheet 16

2. Construction Features

59. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in construction:

11. Have the thermal bridges on the facade been broken?

Yes

No

12. Are roofs and roofs insulated?

Yes

No

13. Has the possibility of placing Trombe walls in single-family homes been studied?

Yes

No

14. Is there the possibility of mounting suspended ceilings?

Yes

No

15. Do you have double glazed windows or an exterior window (double window)?

Yes

No

16. In premises that are air-conditioned, do the windows located on sunny facades have reflective glass with solar laminates?

Yes

No

Technical Sheet 17

2. Construction Features

6. Constructive improvements

60. Constructive improvements justified by energy efficiency, identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion		€	
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

Higher salubrity (health)

Streams are removed

Radiation is reduced

Higher comfort

“Cold wall” is eliminated

Noises are reduced

Elimination of humidity

Others:

3. ENERGY SUPPLIES

Technical Sheet 18

3. Energy supplies

1. Types of energy

61. Energy supplies available to the building

Electricity	diesel C	Piped natural gas
Coal	LPG ³	Other

2. Electrical installations

62. Single-line electrical scheme(s) of the main supply and distribution circuits:

63. Details of the main supply and distribution circuits:

Circuit						
Counter						
Switch (A)						
No. cables x section (mm ²)						
Material: conduct. / isolate						
Installation form						
Length (m)						
Voltage (V): input / output						
Voltage drop (V /%)						
Measurement (Y/N, see section 4 below)						
Observations						

³ LPG: Liquefied Petroleum Gas

Technical Sheet 20

3. Energy supplies

4. Distribution and measurements of energy consumption

66. Distribution of average annual electricity consumption by use:

Use										
Power (kW or %)										
Energy (kWh or %)										

67. Most important parameters and results of electrical measurements:

Installation	
Computer file	
Start date/time	
End date/time	
Record intervals (s)	
Total active consumption (kWh)	
Reactive consumption (kVArh)	
cos φ medium	
Consumption RH active (%)	
Consumption FH active (%)	
Consumption OPH active (%)	
Max active power (kW)	
Average use factor (%)	
Voltage (V)	
Phase balancing	

Technical Sheet 21

3. Energy supplies

5. Fuel storage and distribution facilities

68. Principle scheme of the main fuel storage and distribution circuits:

69. Fuel tank data:

Tank					
Fuel					
Capacity (m³)					
materials					
Age (years)					
Counters or levels					
Surface state					
Leak identification					
Purge form					

Technical Sheet 23

3. Energy supplies

7. Audit on energy supplies

72. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in energy supplies:

1. Has a responsible been appointed to check the invoices for the water and energy supply?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

2. Are monthly water and energy meter readings taken?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

3. Is it verified that the invoiced amounts of water and energy are correct?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

4. Is the electricity supply contract reviewed annually?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

5. Is the energy consumption that takes place at night and on weekends known?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

6. If the contracted rate includes valley billing periods, is consumption planned to take advantage of its economic advantages?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

7. Is the power factor value continuously monitored?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

8. Have offers been requested from different diesel and LPG distributors?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

9. Have offers been requested from different electric energy trading companies?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

10. If you have more than one supply contract, have you considered the possibility of unifying them?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

11. Does the building belong to a diesel or LPG purchasing consortium?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

12. Do you try to avoid buying small quantities of diesel?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

13. In the purchase of diesel and LPG, is seasonal variation in prices taken into account?

Yes	No
------------	-----------

Technical Sheet 24

3. Energy supplies

8. Improvements in energy supplies

73. Improvements in the supply of electricity and / or fuels justified by energy efficiency, identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion		€	
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

More supply guarantee

High security

High salubrity

Less maintenance

More free space

High reliability

Others:

4. HEATING SYSTEM

Technical Sheet 25

4. Heating system

1. General characteristics of the heating system

74. The building has a heating system: Yes No

75. The heating system is:

- a. Exclusive to the building under study
- b. Centralized for the following buildings:

76. Heated area in the study building: %/Total, or m^3

77. Main building heating system (indicate heat generating equipment):

Fuel boilers	Electric radiators or fan-convectors
Electric boilers	Electric accumulators
Electric heat pumps	Other:

78. Distribution system and / or emission of heat from the generation and terminal units

Air	Water or Steam	others
Air conditioners, ducts and diffusers; Autonomous conditioners; Hot air generators; Others:	Water radiators; Fan-coils or air heaters; Radiant floor or ceiling pipes; Others:	Electrical radiator/fan-convector; Electric accumulators; Electric radiant floor or ceiling; Window conditioners; Stoves (gas, kerosene, etc); Multi-split or VRV systems; Others:

Technical Sheet 26

4. Heating system

2. Heat generating equipment

79. Technical characteristics of the main heat equipment:

Designation					
No. of equal equipments					
Service(s)					
Installation location					
Nature of the equipment					
Energy used					
Type					
Carrier fluid					
Burner					
No. of stages					
Fuel flow (kg/s)	Max				
	Min				
Brand					
Model					
Year of manufacture					
Useful power (kW)					
Absorbed (consumed) power (kW)					
Nominal yield (%)					
Stepping power					
Temperature of usage (°C)					
Temperature of departure (°C)					
Pressure of departure (Bar)					
Return temperature (°C)					
Return pressure (Bar)					
Operating regime					
Winter: number of months					
Hours/day of operation					
Observations					

80. Total thermal power installed in heat generating equipment:

kW

Technical Sheet 27

4. Heating system

3. Heat emitting equipment

81. Technical characteristics of the main heat emitting equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipment				
Zone(s)/Local				
Nature of the equipment				
Fluid				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Useful power (kW)				
Flow (Nm ³ /h)				
Input temperature (°C)				
Output temperature (°C)				
Observations				

82. Total thermal power installed in heat emitting equipment:

kW

4. Pumping equipment

83. Technical characteristics of the pumping equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipment				
Zone(s)/Local				
Installation location				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Power (kW)				
Flow (L/s)				
Rotation speed (rpm)				
Hours/day of operation				
Observations				

84. total installed power in pumping equipment:

kW

Technical Sheet 28

4. Heating system

5. Pipelines

85. Technical characteristics of the pipes:

Pipelines					
Use					
Material					
Class/Standard					
Thermal insulation type					
Exterior termination type					
Average fluid service temperature (°C)					
Working pressure					

6. Heating scheme(s)

86. Scheme(s) of the boiler room, fluid distribution, etc. of heating:

7. Heating maintenance

87. Maintenance operations carried out periodically in the heating installation:

There is no maintenance;

Only basic checks are performed;

There is a full maintenance contract;

Others:

Technical Sheet 29

4. Heating system

8. Heating regulation

88. Existing heating regulation systems:

Fully manual control
Thermostat for the entire system
Local or zone thermostat
Control unit programmable by external probe
Remote management or remote control

Programmable clock for the whole system
Chrono-thermostat for the entire system
Thermostat in each terminal unit
Computer centralized management
Others:

89. Control and regulation system control points:

DESCRIPTION	DI ⁸	AI ⁹	DO ¹⁰	AO ¹¹	SO ¹²	CT ¹³
Heated areas						
Average ambient temperature of the area						
Ambient relative humidity of the area						
Hot water production system						
Boiler start/stop command for heating support						
State/general alarm heating boilers						
Start/stop command for 2 primary hot water pumps						
State/alarm for 2 primary hot water pumps						
Lack of pressure / water signal in primary hot water circuit						
Water return temperature signal to boilers						
Boiler water outlet temperature signal						
Command to automatic hot water valves						
Lime automatic water valve regulation command						
Limit switches automatic hot water valves						
Secondary pumping and distribution circuits						
Hot water secondary pumps start / stop command						
Status / alarm secondary hot water pumps						
Reading hot water / circuit flow temperature						
Reading hot water / circuit return temperature						
Consumption meter						
General water meter						
Water supply meter to facilities						
General electric energy meter						
General gas supply meter						

⁸ DI: Digital input

⁹ AI: Analog input

¹⁰ DO: Digital output

¹¹ AO: Analog output

¹² SO: Suspension output

¹³ CT: Counter

Technical Sheet 30

4. Heating system

90. Storage conditions for heating (winter season):

Space	Temperature (°C)	Humidity (% HR)	Observations

9. Heating quality

91. The temperature is in general:

Adequate

Higher

Lower

92. Possible deficiencies in heating distribution and quality:

Heat is poorly distributed

The environment is excessively dry

The system is slow, it has a lot of inertia

The system is unreliable (many breakdowns)

There are sanitary problems

Others:

Technical Sheet 31

4. Heating system

10. Combustion analysis of fuel boilers

93. Results of the analysis of combustion and condition of chimneys of fuel boilers:

Designation					
frontal area (m ²)					
Posterior area (m ²)					
Lateral area (m ²)					
Boiler materials					
Chimney material					
Chimney surface temperature (°C)					
Smoke temperature (°C)					
Average frontal temperature (°C)					
Post average temperature (°C)					
Average lateral temperature (°C)					
Opacity Index					
Chimney draft (mm.c.a.)					
O ₂ concentration (% by volume)					
CO concentration (% by volume)					
NO _x concentration (% by volume)					
SO ₂ concentration (% by volume)					
CO ₂ concentration (% by volume)					
Air excess coefficient / norm (pu)					
Excess air coefficient / equipment (pu)					
Losses from unburned gases (%)					
Solid unburned losses (%)					
Sensitive heat losses in fumes (%)					
Radiation / convection losses (%)					
Combustion yield (%)					
Performance boiler / standard (%)					
Performance boiler / equipment (%)					
Performance boiler / calculations (%)					
General condition of the boiler					
General condition of the chimney					

Technical Sheet 32

4. Heating system

11. Measurements results of indoor winter conditions

94. Winter temperature and humidity measurement results:

Date and hour	Local	Activity	Measurements			
			Interior		Exterior	
			T(°C)	HR (%)	T(°C)	HR (%)

95. Results of other measurements of the heating system:

Date and hour	Parameter	Measurement conditions	Results

Technical Sheet 33

4. Heating system

96. Location of indoor winter conditions on the psychrometric diagram:

Technical Sheet 34

4. Heating system

12. Heating audit

97. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in heating:

- | | |
|---|--|
| <p>1. Is the operation of the boiler checked weekly?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>10. Is the correct functioning of the defrost thermostats of the heat pumps regularly checked?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>2. Is the Boiler Room adequately ventilated?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>11. Is there a program to clean radiators and change fan filters?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>3. Is there a leak detection procedure in place?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>12. Is the official maintenance service realizing an annual review of the boiler?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>4. In installations with several boilers, do some of them turn off in periods with milder weather conditions?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>13. Are all pipes, flanges, and valves insulated?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>5. Is the operation of several boilers in parallel sequenced?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>14. Does the heating and hot water supply come from different boilers?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>6. Is the ignition of the boiler piezoelectric or electronic?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>15. Is the boiler very oversized?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>7. When there is no heat demand in the areas to be heated, do the boilers work continuously?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>16. Is the actual yield of the boilers known?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>8. Are air radiators and diffusers free of obstacles?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>17. Is the heat recovered from the air expelled outside?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>9. Do staff use portable electric heaters without permission?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>18. Has the use of condensing boilers been considered?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |

Technical Sheet 35

4. Heating system

13. Heating improvements

98. Improvements in the heating system justified by energy efficiency, identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion		€	
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

5. REFRIGERATION SYSTEM

Technical Sheet 36

5. Refrigeration system

1. General characteristics of the cooling system

99. The building has a cooling system for the locals: Yes No
100. The cooling system is:
- a. Exclusive to the building under study
 - b. Centralized for the following buildings:
101. Refrigerated area in the building under study is: %/total or m²
102. General type of installation
- Individual equipment
Semi-centralized installation
Centralized installation

103. Main building cooling system (indicate cold generating equipment):

Electric chillers

Electric heat pumps

Others:

104. The cold generating machines are:

Air/Air

Air/Water

Water/Air

Water/Water

105. Cold distribution and emission system and terminal units:

Air	Water	Others
Air conditioners and diffusers	Fan coils	Window conditioners
Autonomous conditioners	Others:	Multi-split conditioners or VRV systems
Others:		Others:

Technical Sheet 37

5. Refrigeration system

2. Cold generating equipment

106. Technical characteristics of the main cold generation equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipments				
Installation location				
Nature of the equipment				
Energy used				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Useful power (kW)				
Absorbed (consumed) power (kW)				
Nominal COP				
Stepping power				
Temperature of usage (°C)				
Temperature of departure (°C)				
Pressure of departure (Bar)				
Return temperature (°C)				
Return pressure (Bar)				
Operating regime				
Summer: number of months				
Winter: number of months				
Observations				

107. Total thermal power installed in cold generating equipment: kW

Technical Sheet 38

5. Refrigeration system

3. Cold emitting equipment

108. Technical characteristics of the main cold generation equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipment				
Installation location				
Nature of the equipment				
Fluid				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Useful power (kW)				
Flow (Nm ³ /h)				
Nominal COP				
Stepping power				
Input temperature(°C)				
Output temperature (°C)				
Observations				

109. Total thermal power installed in cold generating equipment: kW

4. Refrigeration scheme(s)

110. Principles scheme(s) of, machine room, cooling etc.

Technical Sheet 39

5. Refrigeration system

5. Cooling maintenance

111. Maintenance operations carried out periodically in the refrigeration installation:

- There is no maintenance;
- Only basic checks are performed;
- There is a full maintenance contract;
- Others:

6. Refrigeration regulation

112. Existing refrigeration regulation systems:

- | | |
|---|---|
| Fully manual control | Programmable clock for the whole system |
| Thermostat for the entire system | Chrono-thermostat for the entire system |
| Local or zone thermostat | Thermostat in each terminal unit |
| Control unit programmable by external probe | Computer centralized management |
| Remote management or remote control | Others: |

113. Control and regulation system control points:

DESCRIPTION	DI ¹⁴	AI ¹⁵	DO ¹⁶	AO ¹⁷	SO ¹⁸	CT ¹⁹
Heated areas						
Average ambient temperature of the area						
Ambient relative humidity of the area						
Cold production system						
Command start / stop cold generation equipment						
General status / alarm cold generating equipment						
Fluid return temperature signal						
Fluid flow temperature signal						
Consumption accounting						
General water meter						
Water supply meter to facilities						
General electric energy meter						

¹⁴ DI: Digital input

¹⁵ AI: Analog input

¹⁶ DO: Digital output

¹⁷ AO: Analog output

¹⁸ SO: Supervised output

¹⁹ CT: Counter

Technical Sheet 40

5. Refrigeration system

114. Storage conditions for refrigeration (summer season):

Space	Temperature (°C)	Humidity (% HR)	Observations

7. Refrigeration quality

115. The temperature is in general:

Adequate

Higher

Lower

116. Possible deficiencies in cooling distribution and quality:

Cold is poorly distributed

The environment is excessively dry

The system is slow, it has a lot of inertia

The system is unreliable (many breakdowns)

There are sanitary problems

Others:

8. Measurement results of indoor conditions in summer

117. Summer temperature and humidity measurement results:

Date and hour	Local	Activity	Measurements			
			Interior		Exterior	
			T(°C)	HR (%)	T(°C)	HR (%)

Technical Sheet 41

5. Refrigeration system

118. Refrigeration system measurement results:

Date and hour	Parameter	Measurement conditions	Results

119. Location of indoor summer conditions on the psychrometric diagram:

Technical Sheet 42

5. Refrigeration system

9. Refrigeration audit

120. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in refrigeration:

- | | |
|--|---|
| <p>1. Is a weekly check of the chiller room planned?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>9. Does the official maintenance service check the chillers annually?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>2. Are you set up a method for detecting leaks or coolant leaks?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>10. Are the air distribution ducts insulated?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>3. In installations with several chillers, are these switched off successively as the weather conditions moderate?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>11. Are all pipes, flanges and valves insulated in the refrigeration circuit?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>4. Do the chillers operate continuously when there is no demand for cold in the areas to be conditioned?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>12. Is the cold production machinery oversized?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>5. Are fan coils and air diffusers free of obstacles?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>13. Is the power of the chillers fractionated?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>6. Do staff use portable "penguins" without authorization when there is a central air conditioning system?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>14. Is the air conditioning of special premises separated from the rest of the rooms?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>7. Are there uncontrolled heat sources in the conditioned rooms?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | <p>15. Is free air cooling taken advantage of at halftime?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> |
| <p>8. Is there a cleaning program to maintain the air ducts and change the dirty filters of the fan-coils?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yes No</p> | |

Technical Sheet 43

5. Refrigeration system

10. Cooling system improvements

- 121. Improvements in the refrigeration system justified by energy efficiency identified and evaluated technically and economically:**

Identification		
Description		
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity
		Unit
		(%)
	Combustible	Quantity
		Unit
		(%)
Total economic savings		€/year
Total inversion		€
Simple payback period (years)		
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)		

- 122. Other advantages of this improvement:**

More comfort

High security

High salubrity

Best distributed cold

High reliability

Others:

6. VENTILATION SYSTEM

Technical Sheet 44

6. Ventilation system

1. General characteristics of the ventilation system

- | | | Yes | No |
|-------------|--|-----|----|
| 123. | The building has a ventilation system: | | |
| 124. | The ventilation system is: | | |
| | a. Exclusive to the building under study | | |
| | b. Centralized for the following buildings: | | |
| 125. | Independence of the ventilation system: | | |
| | It is integrated into the heating system | | |
| | It is integrated into the air conditioning system | | |
| | It is an independent system | | |
| 126. | Type of ventilation: | | |
| | Mechanics | | |
| | with mechanical admission | | |
| | with mechanical extraction | | |
| | balanced | | |
| | natural | | |
| | Hybrid | | |
| 127. | Nature of the building's ventilation system (indicate basic form of air renewal): | | |
| | Forced supply of the cooling air by means of supply fans | | |
| | Forced extraction of stale air using exhaust fans | | |
| | Extraction of stale air by natural draft using deck extractors | | |

Technical Sheet 45

6. Ventilation system

128. Air circulation:

Air circulates from dry to wet rooms

129. Admission:

There are openings for admission in:

Dining rooms

Bedrooms

Living rooms

Others

Are directly connected to the outside

Are communicated through an intake duct

The aerators are at a distance from the ground of

Class and use of carpentry as intake (admission) openings

Carpentry class	Use of admission openings
Class 0	Opening joints Other
Class 1	Opening joints Other
Class 2	Openings equipped with aerators Fixed carpentry openings Others
Class 3	Openings equipped with aerators Fixed carpentry openings Others
Class 4	Openings equipped with aerators Fixed carpentry openings Others

Technical Sheet 46

6. Ventilation system

130. Extraction:

There are extraction openings in:

toilets

kitchens

others

Are directly connected to the outside

Are connected to extraction ducts

Are at a distance from the ceiling of

Are at a distance from any corner to vertical corner of

The extraction ducts are not shared with other uses premises except with the storage rooms

In premises with compartmentalized extraction, indicate the situation of:

Passage openings

Extraction opening

131. Passage:

The partitions located between the premises with admission and the premises with extraction have access openings

The premises with various uses have in each area destined for a different use the corresponding openings

Technical Sheet 47

6. Ventilation system

2. Ventilation equipment

132. Technical characteristics of the main ventilation equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipment				
Service(s)				
Installation location				
Nature of the equipment				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Total air flow (m ³ /h)				
Refreshment air flow (m ³ /h)				
Useful power (kW)				
Absorbed (consumed) power (kW)				
Nominal yield (%)				
Air filter				
Observations				

133. Total capacity of air renewal m³/h
134. Total thermal power installed in air renewal equipment kW

Technical Sheet 48

6. Ventilation system

135. Technical characteristics of the intake openings:

OPENINGS				
Location				
Identification				
Type				
Communication with outside				
Effective area dimensions (cm ²)				
Type of aerator				
Nominal flow (L/s)				
Observations				

136. Technical characteristics of the ducts:

DUCTS				
Location				
Identification				
Use				
Longitude (m)				
Dimensions (cm * cm)				
Area (m ²)				
Flow (L/s)				
Shooting class				
Observations				

Technical Sheet 49

6. Ventilation system

3. Ventilation quality

137. Possible deficiencies in ventilation distribution and quality:

Air velocity is excessive	The system is noisy
Poor ambient air quality	It is poorly regulated
Causes health problems	The system is unreliable, has breakdowns
Others:	

138. Indoor air quality category:

It is unknown

IDA 1- optimum quality air

IDA 2 - good quality air

IDA 3 - medium quality air

IDA 4 - low quality air

139. Outdoor air quality:

It is unknown

ODA 1- pure air that may temporarily contain solid particles

ODA 2 - air with high concentrations of particles

ODA 3 - air with high concentrations of gaseous pollutants

ODA 4 - air with high concentrations of gaseous and particulate pollutants

ODA 5 - air with very high concentrations of gaseous and particulate pollutants

140. Extraction air:

It is unknown

AE 1- low level of pollution

AE 2 - moderate level of pollution

AE 3 - high level of pollution

AE 4 - very high level of pollution

Technical Sheet 50

6. Ventilation system

4. Ventilation schemes

141. Principle diagram of machine room ventilation, etc.

5. Measurement results of ventilation conditions

142. Measurement results for each of the premises:

Premise (local)	
Activity	
No. of occupants	
Local longitude (m)	
Local width (m)	
Local height (m)	
Minimum required ventilation flow (L/s)	
Measured ventilation flow (L/s)	
Observations	

Technical Sheet 51

6. Ventilation system

6. Maintenance of ventilation

143. Maintenance operations carried out periodically in the ventilation installation:

There is no maintenance

Filters are cleaned and / or replaced periodically

Ducts, exchangers, boxes, etc. are periodically cleaned.

There is a full maintenance contract

Others:

144. The maintenance plan contains the following operations:

Installation element	Operation	Frequency	Observations
Ducts	Cleaning Checking the apparent tightness		
Opening	Cleaning		
Hybrid, mechanical and extractor vacuum cleaners	Cleaning Functionality status review		
Filters	Status review Cleaning or replacement		
Control systems	Review of the status of your automation		

Technical Sheet 52

6. Ventilation system

7. Ventilation audit

145. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in ventilation

1. Are unnecessary fans turned off?

Yes

No

2. Are individual fans used in an unauthorized way?

Yes

No

3. Are natural ventilation systems used?

Yes

No

4. Is the operating time of the exhaust fans in premises such as toilets and kitchens controlled?

Yes

No

5. Is the operating time of garage fans controlled?

Yes

No

6. Are extractors equipped with automatic shutters?

Yes

No

7. Have you checked the cleanliness of the inside ventilation ducts?

Yes

No

8. Has it been verified that the ventilation flows are not excessive?

Yes

No

9. Is air recirculation planned?

Yes

No

Technical Sheet 53

6. Ventilation system

146. Improvements in the ventilation system justified by energy efficiency identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion		€	
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

7. SANITARY HOT WATER SYSTEM (DHW)

Technical Sheet 54

7. Sanitary hot water system

1. General characteristics of the DHW system

147. The building has some DHW production system: Yes No
148. DHW's production system is:
- a. Exclusive to the building under study
 - b. Centralized for the following buildings:
149. Maximum DHW demand covered: L/ h, or L/ day at °C
150. Services served by the DHW:
- | | |
|---------------------|-----------------------|
| Laundries and sinks | Showers |
| Washing machines | heated swimming pools |
| Others: | |
151. DHW main production system (primary heating form):
- Electric thermo(s) accumulator(s)
- Instant heater for combustible ()
- Domestic mixed boilers for combustible ()
- Central boilers for combustible () shared with heating
- Central boilers for combustible () with exclusive dedication
- Others:

2. Production, accumulation and distribution of DHW

152. DHW production system (form of secondary heating):
- | | |
|--|--|
| Plate heat exchanger <input type="checkbox"/> | Inter-accumulator tank <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Exchanger incorporated (mixed boiler) <input type="checkbox"/> | Direct production (electric, ac., Etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> |
153. DHW distribution system from production to point of consumption:
- Direct from thermos, tank or boiler
- Through recirculation circuit

Technical Sheet 55

7. Sanitary hot water system

154. Characteristics of the DHW heating equipment:

Designation				
No. of equal equipment				
Service(s)				
Nature of the equipment				
Energy used				
Type				
Burner				
Brand				
Model				
Year of manufacture				
Useful power (kW)				
Absorbed (consumed) power (kW)				
Nominal yield (%)				
Stepping power				
Temperature of usage (°C)				
Temperature of departure (°C)				
Pressure of departure (Bar)				
Return temperature (°C)				
Return pressure (Bar)				
Observations				

155. Characteristics of the DHW accumulation tanks:

Designation				
No. of equal equipment				
Service(s)				
Maximum capacity (l)				
Average temperature (°C)				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Materials				
Year of manufacture				
Observations				

Technical Sheet 56

7. Sanitary hot water system

3. DHW schemes:

156. Principle scheme(s) of machines room...etc, of DHW:

4. DHW maintenance

157. Maintenance operations carried out periodically at the DHW facility:

There is no maintenance;

Only basic checks are performed;

There is a full maintenance contract;

Others:

Technical Sheet 57

7. Sanitary hot water system

5. DHW regulation

158. Forms of regulation of the production of DHW:

Control by manual mixing	Control over instantaneous production temperature
Accumulation temperature probe	Control over output temperature of the tank
Timed shower buttons	thermostatic Faucet
Zone thermostatic valves	Centralized computer control
Remote management or remote control	Others:

159. DHW setpoint conditions:

Point	setpoint temperature (°C)		Observations
	Winter	Summer	

6. DHW quality

160. The temperature of DHW is in general:

Adequate

Higher

Lower

161. Possible deficiencies in DHW distribution and quality:

The DHW is poorly distributed	Flow and/or temperature oscillations
Capacity is low (runs out quickly)	The system is unreliable (breakdowns)
The A.C. S. takes time to reach the point of consumption	Others:

Technical Sheet 58

7. Sanitary hot water system

7. DHW audit

162. Answer the following questions about energy efficiency in DHW:

- | | | |
|--|------------|-----------|
| 1. Are the staff careless and leave taps badly closed? | Yes | No |
| 2. Are leaky faucets repaired immediately? | Yes | No |
| 3. Are pipes periodically checked for leaks? | Yes | No |
| 4. Is the hot water distribution temperature excessive? | Yes | No |
| 5. Is hot water used where cold water is equally effective? | Yes | No |
| 6. During vacation periods, do all water heating systems turn off? | Yes | No |
| 7. Are the equipment that controls the DHW production system correctly programmed? | Yes | No |
| 8. Is there a non-return valve in the pipeline connecting the boiler to the distribution tank or to the collector? | Yes | No |
| 9. When a large number of storage tanks are available, has their use been studied from the point of view of energy efficiency? | Yes | No |
| 10. Are the storage tanks isolated? | Yes | No |

Technical Sheet 59

7. Sanitary hot water system

161. Questions about energy efficiency in the DHW (continued)

11. And are the hot water distribution pipes insulated?

Yes

No

12. Are programmer clocks used to control the period of operation of the intercoms?

Yes

No

13. Is there control over the operating time of the circulation pumps?

Yes

No

14. Do they shut all taps correctly?

Yes

No

15. Are flow reducers used in faucets for sinks, bidets, sinks and showers?

Yes

No

16. In dual-control showers, has the possibility of installing flow switches been studied?

Yes

No

17. In the men's toilets, do the urinals have flowmeters?

Yes

No

18. Can the flow of the tanks be regulated?

Yes

No

19. Are all hoses closed after use?

Yes

No

20. Is the water heated near the consumption point?

Yes

No

21. Have you considered the option of exchanging the water tank for an exchanger?

Yes

No

Technical Sheet 60

7. Sanitary hot water system

8. DHW installation improvements

162. Improvements in the installation of DHW justified by energy efficiency identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion		€	
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

More comfort

Higher salubrity

Higher security

Higher reliability

Faster

Others:

8. INSTALLATION OF THERMAL SOLAR ENERGY

Technical Sheet 61

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

1. General characteristics of solar thermal energy installation

163. **The building has thermal solar energy:** Yes No
164. **The thermal solar energy system is:**
- Exclusive to the building under study
 - Centralized for the following buildings:
165. **The main end uses of solar thermal are:**
- | DHW | Heated pool | Heating |
|-----|-------------|---------|
|-----|-------------|---------|
166. **Total effective area of the installation:** m²
167. **Installation location:**
- General
 - Overlap
 - Architectural integration
168. **Reference temperature of DHW demand:** °C
169. **Auxiliary support system:**
- General
 - Joule effect
 - Diesel
 - Propane
 - Natural Gas
 - Others:
170. **General data of the DHW demand:**

No. of consumptions	
Specific consumption (L/ day for ref. unit)	
Demand reference at 60 °C DHW (L/day)	
Accumulation volume (L)	

Technical Sheet 62

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

171. Minimum required solar contribution: %
172. Solar contribution of the system:

Month	DHW demand (L)	Energy demand (kWh)	Solar contribution (kWh)	Solar contribution/demand * 100 (%)
January				
February				
March				
April				
May				
June				
July				
August				
September				
October				
November				
December				
Total				

2. Scheme of the solar thermal installation

Technical Sheet 63

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

3. absorption system

173. Scheme of the solar thermal installation:

No. of solar collectors			
Dimensions (A*L, (m))			
Effective collector area (m²)			
Collector efficiency factor			
Global loss coefficient (W/m² °C)			
Orientation (°)			
Losses	For orientation or inclination (%)		
	for shading (%)		
	Total (%)		
State			
Corrosion			
Supports			
Hydraulic piping			
Circulating fluid			
Temperatures	Collector	Input	Output

Technical Sheet 64

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

174. Technical characteristics of solar collectors:

Brand	
Model	
Type	
Cover	
Effective collector area (m²)	
Collector efficiency factor	
Global loss coefficient (W/m² °C)	

4. Connection scheme of solar collectors:

Technical Sheet 65

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

5. Hydraulic circuit

175. Characteristics of the primary circuit:

Location		
Longitude (m)		
Diameter (m)		
Isolations		
Leaks		
Corrosions		
Flows (L/s)		
Temperatures (°C)		
Pump	Nominal flow (L/s)	
	Power (kW)	
	Location	
Valves	Type	
	Placement	
Other auxiliaries		
Observations		

176. Characteristics of the secondary circuit:

Location		
Longitude (m)		
Diameter (m)		
Isolations		
Leaks		
Corrosions		
Flows (L/s)		
Temperatures (°C)		
Pump	Nominal flow (L/s)	
	Power (kW)	
	Location	
Valves	Type	
	Placement	
Other auxiliaries		
Observations		

Technical Sheet 66

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

6. Exchange system

177. Technical characteristics of the exchanger:

Brand				
Model				
Number				
Location				
Type				
Minimal power (kW)				
Exchange area				
Nominal flows (L/h)	Collector side		Tank side	
Maximum flows (L/h)	Collector side		Tank side	
Isolations	Type			
	Thickness			
	State			
Temperatures (°C)	Collector input		Collector output	
	Tank input		Tank output	
Union of probes				
State				
Leaks				
Corrosions				
Observations				

Technical Sheet 67

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

7. Accumulation system

178. Technical characteristics of the exchanger:

Brand				
Model				
Location				
Geometry				
Volume (L)				
Isolations	Type			
	Thickness			
	State			
Temperatures (°C)	Exchanger input		Exchanger output	
	Boiler /consumption input		Boiler /consumption output	
Union of probes				
State				
Leaks				
Corrosions				
Observations				

Technical Sheet 69

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

10. Maintenance of the solar thermal energy system

182. Maintenance operations carried out periodically in the solar thermal energy installation:

There is no maintenance

Only basic checks are performed

A surveillance plan exists and is applied

A maintenance plan exists and is applied

183. The surveillance plan contains the following operations:

Installation element	Operation	Frequency
Collectors	Crystal Cleaning Observation of condensations on crystals Visual inspection of joint condition Visual inspection of absorber Visual inspection of the structure	
Primary circuit	Visual inspection of piping, insulation and filling system Emptying the air from the manual drain bottle	
Secondary circuit	Visual inspection of the thermometer Visual inspection of pipe and insulation Purged sludge accumulation bottom tank	

Technical Sheet 70

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

184. The maintenance plan contains the following operations:

Installation element	Operation	Frequency
Collectors	Visual inspection of differences on original Visual inspection of differences between collectors	
Crystals	Visual inspection of condensation and dirt	
Joints	Visual inspection cracks and deformations	
Absorber	Visual inspection for corrosion and deformation	
Case	Visual inspection for deficiencies, oscillations, breathing windows	
Connections	Visual inspection for leaks	
Structure	Visual inspection degradation, corrosion starts, tighten screws	
Tank	Presence of sludge in the bottom	
Sacrificial anodes	Wear check	
Printed current anodes	Proof of proper operation	
Insulation	Moisture free check	
Plate exchanger	Efficiency and performance control Cleaning	
Coil exchanger	Efficiency and performance control Cleaning	
Coolant fluid	Density and PH check	
Watertightness	Carry out a pressure test	
Exterior insulation	Visual inspection degradation protection joints and absence of moisture	
Interior insulation	Visual inspection of joints and absence of moisture	
Automatic drain	Correct operation and cleaning	
Manual drain	Empty the air from the bottle	
Pump	Watertightness	
Closed expansion vessel	Pressure check	
Open expansion vessel	Level check	
Filling system	Operating performance test	
Cut valve	Check operation of performances (open and close) to avoid jamming	
Security valve	Operating performance test	
Electric board	Always check tightly closed to avoid dust entry	
Differential control	Operating performance test	
Thermostat	Operating performance test	
Measurement system verification	Operating performance test	
Auxiliary system	Operating performance test	
Temperature probes	Operating performance test	

Technical Sheet 71

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

11. Audit of the solar thermal energy system

185. Answer the following questions about the energy efficiency of the solar thermal energy installation:

1. Do collectors look deteriorated or very dirty?

Yes

No

2. Does the hydraulic circuit observe a proper state of isolation?

Yes

No

3. Is the hydraulic circuit properly balanced?

Yes

No

4. Are there any leaks?

Yes

No

5. Are the angle and orientation of the collector optimal?

Yes

No

6. Does the DHW production auxiliary support system work only when needed?

Yes

No

7. Is there any corrosion?

Yes

No

Technical Sheet 72

8. Installation of thermal solar energy

12. Improvements in the installation of solar thermal energy

186. Improvements in the installation of solar thermal energy justified by energy efficiency identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion	€		
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

9. COGENERATION FACILITY

Technical Sheet 73

9. Cogeneration facility

1. General characteristics of the plant

187. The building has a cogeneration facility: Yes No
188. General plant data:

Year of construction	
No. of operating hours	
Performing Overhaul (year, number of hours)	
Promoter, engineering and beneficiaries or partners of the plant	
Operation and management modality	
Grid connection	

2. Characteristics of the cogeneration group

189. Technical characteristics of the cogeneration group:

Group characteristics	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type 4
Turbine (T) or alternate combustion engine (MCI)				
Brand and model				
Combustible (diesel, gas, biogas...)				
Combustible consumption (kW)				
Nominal electrical power (kW)				
Electrical yield				
Heat dissipated in cooling circuit only (MCI) (kW)				
Heat in exhaust gases (kW)				
Sum of useful heat (kW)				
Alternator: number of poles, voltage and frequency				
Number of equal motor-generator groups				

Technical Sheet 74

9. Cogeneration facility

3. Characteristics of the electrical installation

190. Grid connection characteristics:

The energy produced through the common transformer is exported, billed for the difference in meters.

The energy produced is exported through an independent transformer for cogeneration.

The energy produced in low voltage is exported, through a connection point authorized by the electrical distribution company.

The energy produced is self-consumed, injecting into the general low voltage panel.

Other options:

191. Characteristics of major equipment:

Transformer	
Power (kW)	
Transformer voltage (V)	
Common or independent (C/I)	
Measurement counter (Yes/No)	
Protection and measurement	
Brand and model of the counter	
Telemetry (Yes/No)	
Protection cells	
Alternator	
Mechanical power on axis (kW)	
Nominal power on alternator terminals (kVA)	
Effective power at $\cos \varphi = 0.8$	
Effective power at $\cos \varphi = 1$	
Rotation speed (rpm)	
Pole pairs	
Yield at $\cos \varphi = 0.8$	
Yield at $\cos \varphi = 1$	
Number of phases	
Voltage (V)	
Frequency	

Technical Sheet 75

9. Cogeneration facility

192. Electrical scheme of the system:

4. Characteristics of the mechanical installation

193. Pumping groups:

Pumping groups				
No. of equal equipment				
Installation location				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of production				
Power (kW)				
Flow (L/s)				
Rotation speed (rpm)				
Operation (hours/day)				
Observations				

194. Pipelines:

Pipelines				
Use				
Material				
Class/norm				
Thermal insulation type				
Exterior insulation type				
Average fluid service temperature (°C)				
Work pressure				

Technical Sheet 76

9. Cogeneration facility

195. Plate exchangers:

Exchanger				
No. of equal equipment				
Installation location				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of production				
Power (kW)				
Input/output temperature 1st (°C)				
Input/output temperature 2nd (°C)				
Flows 1st/2nd (m ³ /h)				
Observations				

196. Smoke recovery boilers:

boiler				
No. of equal equipment				
Installation location				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of production				
Nominal yield				
Smoke flow (m ³ /h)				
Power (kW)				
Smoke input/output temperature (°C)				
Water/steam input/output temperature (°C)				
Water/steam flow (m ³ /h)				
Observations				

Technical Sheet 77

9. Cogeneration facility

197. Absorption chillers:

Chiller				
No. of equal equipment				
Installation location				
Type				
Brand				
Model				
Year of production				
Outlet temperature of cooled water (°C)				
Flow (m ³)				
Cooling power (kW)				
Intlet temperature of cooled water (°C)				
Tower outlet temperature (°C)				
Tower water flow (m ³ /h)				
Return water inlet temperature (°C)				
Return water outlet temperature (°C)				
Hot water inlet temperature (°C)				
Hot water outlet temperature (°C)				
Flow (L/s)				
Electric consumption (kVA)				
Observations				

198. Installation schematic:

Technical Sheet 78

9. Cogeneration facility

5. Operating parameters

199. Annual parameters obtained by the system:

Electric power	
Exported electrical energy (kWh/year)	
Self-consumed electric energy (kWh/year)	
Annual electricity production (E) (kWh/year)	
Seasonal electrical yield	
Instantaneous electrical yield (measured by the auditor)	
Heat	
Annual production of useful heat (V) (kWh/year)	
Seasonal thermal yield	
Instantaneous thermal yield (measured by the auditor)	
combustible	
Annual combustible consumption (Q) (kWh/year)	
Availability	
Annual availability of the plant (h/year)	

200. Calculation of equivalent electrical yield:

	kWh/year
Annual electricity production (E)	
Annual production of useful heat (V)	
Annual combustible consumption (Q)	

Technical Sheet 79

9. Cogeneration facility

201. Measurement results of the most important parameters:

Residual heat measurement. Recovery boiler	Smokes inlet temperature (°C)			
	Smokes outlet temperature (°C)			
	Gas flow (kg/h)			
Measurement of heat transfer in plate exchangers	Secondary water inlet temperature (°C)			
	Secondary water outlet temperature (°C)			
	secondary water flow (m ³ /h)			
Electricity	Electric power produced, measured at generator terminals (kWh)			
	Electric energy produced, measured in the central bars (kWh)			

202. Results of measurements of other significant parameters of cogeneration:

Date/hour	Parameter	Measured conditions	Results

Technical Sheet 80

9. Cogeneration facility

203. Thermography realized:

Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification
Thermography No.: Identification	Thermography No.: Identification

204. Comments:

205. Observations:

Technical Sheet 81

9. Cogeneration facility

6. Maintenance of the cogeneration system

206. Maintenance operations carried out periodically at the cogeneration facility:

There is no maintenance

Only basic checks are performed

There is an operation and surveillance service with a validity period of:

There is a remote management system and automatic fault report with an average intervention time of:

There is a corrective maintenance service

There is a comprehensive maintenance service (preventive + corrective -including in this the cost of the pieces)

Maintenance price: € /kWh generated

207. Maintenance plan:

A maintenance plan for the cogeneration facility exists and is applied

The maintenance plan is integrated together with the building

The maintenance plan is carried out by the same company that develops the maintenance of the building

The plan is attached within the audit

Technical Sheet 82

9. Cogeneration facility

7. Cogeneration system audit

208. Answer the following questions about the energy efficiency of the cogeneration installation:

- | | | |
|---|------------|-----------|
| 1. Is the operation of the motor-generator or turbine group reviewed weekly? | Yes | No |
| 2. Is the condition of the recovery boiler (or exchanger) analysed? | Yes | No |
| 3. Has the possibility of producing cold with an absorption machine been analysed? | Yes | No |
| 4. Is all available heat used? | Yes | No |
| 5. Is the combustible supply system regularly checked? | Yes | No |
| 6. Is the maintenance work of the motor-generator set (or turbine) carried out regularly according to the manufacturer's guidelines? | Yes | No |
| 7. Are thermographic inspections carried out to analyse the insulation status of equipment, valves and distribution networks? | Yes | No |
| 8. Is combustion analysis performed? | Yes | No |
| 9. Is there oversizing of equipment? | Yes | No |
| 10. Is reactive energy regulated by capacitor banks? | Yes | No |
| 11. If electric energy is self-consumed, has the possibility of exporting energy under the special regime of electric energy producers been analysed? | Yes | No |
| 12. Is the cogeneration room properly ventilated? | Yes | No |

Technical Sheet 83

9. Cogeneration facility

8. Improvements in the cogeneration installation

209. Improvements in the cogeneration facility justified by energy efficiency identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion	€		
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

10. PHOTOVOLTAIC SOLAR ENERGY SYSTEM

Technical Sheet 84

10. Photovoltaic solar energy system

1. General characteristics of the photovoltaic solar energy installation

- | | | | |
|-------------|--|----------------------|-----------|
| 210. | The building has a photovoltaic solar installation: | Yes | No |
| 211. | The photovoltaic solar energy production system is: | | |
| | a. Exclusive to the building under study | | |
| | b. Centralized for the following buildings: | | |
| 212. | The electrical energy produced is used to: | | |
| | self use | Grid supply | |
| 213. | Total surface of the installation | m² | |
| 214. | Peak power of the installation | kW | |
| 215. | Minimum power required | kW | |
| 216. | Installation location: | | |
| | General | | |
| | Overlap | | |
| | Architectural integration | | |

2. Diagram of the photovoltaic solar installation

Technical Sheet 85

10. Photovoltaic solar energy system

3. Photovoltaic generator system

217. General characteristics of the photovoltaic solar energy system:

No. of modules		
Dimensions (m)		
Total effective area (m ²)		
Peak power (kW)		
Inclination (°)		
Orientation		
Losses	By orientation and inclination	
	By shading (%)	
	Total (%)	
General state		
Corrosions		
supports		

218. Technical characteristics of the collector:

Brand	
Model	
Type	
Effective collector area (m ²)	
Nominal power (kW)	
Yield	

Technical Sheet 86

10. Photovoltaic solar energy system

4. Inverter

219. Technical characteristics of the inverter:

Brand	
Model	
Type	
No. of inverters	
Total nominal power (kW)	
Nominal power of the inverter (kW)	

5. Maintenance of the photovoltaic solar energy system

220. Maintenance operations carried out periodically in the solar thermal energy installation:

There is no maintenance

Only basic checks are performed

A surveillance plan exists and is applied

A maintenance plan exists and is applied

221. Technical characteristics of the control system:

Electrical protections checking

Module status check: checking of the situation with respect to the original project and checking of the protection status

Inverter status check: operation, signalling lamps, alarms, etc.

Checking of the mechanical condition of cables and terminals, plates, transformers, fans / extractors, unions, retightening and cleaning

Technical Sheet 87

10. Photovoltaic solar energy system

6. Audit of the photovoltaic solar energy system

222. Answer the following questions about the energy efficiency of the photovoltaic solar energy installation:

1. Are the collectors look deteriorated or very dirty?

Yes

No

2. Is the angle and orientation of the collectors optimal?

Yes

No

3. Is there any corrosion?

Yes

No

7. Improvements in the installation of photovoltaic solar energy

223. Improvements in the installation of photovoltaic solar energy justified by energy efficiency identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Identification			
Description			
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
	Combustible	Quantity	
		Unit	
		(%)	
Total economic savings		€/year	
Total inversion		€	
Simple payback period (years)			
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)			

Other advantages of this improvement:

11. CONCLUSIONS

Technical Sheet 88

11. Conclusions

1. Summary of improvements

224. Summary of the improvements justified by energy efficiency, identified and evaluated technically and economically:

Area		Construction Features	Energy supplies	Heating system	Refrigeration system	Ventilation system
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity				
		Unit				
		(%)				
	Combustible	Quantity				
		Unit				
		(%)				
Total economic savings		€/year				
Total inversion		€				
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)						
Observations						

Technical Sheet 89

11. Conclusions

224. Summary of the improvements justified by energy efficiency, identified and evaluated technically and economically (continued):

Area			Sanitary hot water system	Installation of thermal solar energy	Cogeneration facility	Photovoltaic solar energy system	Total
Annual energy savings	Electricity	Quantity					
		Unit					
		(%)					
	Combustible	Quantity					
		Unit					
		(%)					
Total economic savings		€/year					
Total inversion		€					
CO2 emissions avoided (Tonne/year)							
Observations							

Technical Sheet 92

11. Conclusions

4. General observations of the auditor

Appendices

Schemes

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